

Additional file

Anticoagulants for thrombosis prophylaxis in acutely ill hospitalised patients: a network meta-analysis

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Figure S1. Convergence: mortality

Figure S2. Convergence: venous thromboembolism

Figure S3. Major bleeding

Figure S4. Convergence: serious adverse events

Figure S5. PRISMA2020 flow diagram

Figure S6. Node-splitting: mortality

CrI: credible interval; lmwh_low: low dose low-molecular-weight heparin; lmwh_int: Intermediate dose low-molecular-weight heparin; ufh_low: low dose unfractionated heparin; ufh_int: intermediate dose unfractionated heparin.

Note to Figure S6 (Node-splitting analysis of mortality):

The node-splitting analysis of mortality shows no evidence of statistical inconsistency.

Figure S7. Node-splitting: venous thromboembolism

CrI: credible interval; lmwh_low: low dose low-molecular-weight heparin; lmwh_int: Intermediate dose low-molecular-weight heparin; ufh_low: low dose unfractionated heparin; ufh_int: intermediate dose unfractionated heparin.

Note to Figure S7 (Node-splitting analysis of venous thromboembolism)

The node-splitting analysis of VTE shows no evidence of statistical inconsistency. The initial node-splitting analysis of the VTE data was hampered by numerical instability due to sparse events. The current analysis includes a continuity adjustment, in which we added 0.5 to all cells in the 2x2 table of RCTs with events in at least one group but zero events in another group.

Figure S8. Node-splitting: major bleeding

CrI: credible interval; lmwh_low: low dose low-molecular-weight heparin; lmwh_int: Intermediate dose low-molecular-weight heparin; ufh_low: low dose unfractionated heparin; ufh_int: intermediate dose unfractionated heparin.

Note to Figure S8 (Node-splitting analysis of major bleeding):

The nodes-splitting analysis of major bleeding shows evidence of statistical inconsistency, mainly in the direct ufh_low vs lmwh_low comparison. Closer inspection reveals that this comparison is informed by 3 studies [1–3] that detected only 1 bleeding event in the lmwh_low arm, whereas they detected 8 bleeding events in the ufh_low arms. This translates into a very large and imprecise direct estimate, that also influences the indirect estimate of ufh_int vs lmwh_low. Although it is possible (and maybe even likely) that ufh_low truly performs worse than lmwh_low, it appears that in this case the statistical inconsistency was mainly driven by sparse events and sampling variation. Therefore we do not regard this as problematic - and judge that this finding does not represent ‘true’ underlying incoherence

Figure S9. Node-splitting: serious adverse events

CrI: credible interval; lmwh_low: low dose low-molecular-weight heparin; lmwh_int: Intermediate dose low-molecular-weight heparin; ufh_low: low dose unfractionated heparin; ufh_int: intermediate dose unfractionated heparin.

Note to Figure S9 (Node-splitting analysis of serious adverse events):

The node-splitting analysis of serious adverse shows no evidence of statistical inconsistency, but some of the estimates appear numerically unstable. Adding a continuity correction did not solve this problem.

Figure S10. Within-study bias: mortality

Within-study bias assessment for mortality. The y-axis displays each comparison. The x-axis represents the percentage of studies with respective low risks of bias (green) versus unclear or high risks of bias (red). Doac: direct oral anticoagulants; Lmwh_low: low dose low-molecular-weight heparin; Lmwh_int: Intermediate dose low-molecular-weight heparin; pentasach: pentasaccharides; ufh_low: low dose unfractionated heparin; ufh_int: intermediate dose unfractionated heparin

Figure S11. Within-study bias: venous thromboembolism

Within-study bias assessment for venous thromboembolism. The y-axis displays each comparison. The x-axis represents the percentage of studies with respective low risks of bias (green) versus unclear or high risks of bias (red). Doac: direct oral anticoagulants; Lmwh_low: low dose low-molecular-weight heparin; lmwh_int: Intermediate dose low-molecular-weight heparin; pentasach: pentasaccharides; ufh_low: low dose unfractionated heparin; ufh_int: intermediate dose unfractionated heparin

Figure S12. Within-study bias: major bleeding

Within-study bias assessment for bleeding. The y-axis displays each comparison. The x-axis represents the percentage of studies with respective low risks of bias (green) versus unclear or high risks of bias (red). Doac: direct oral anticoagulants; Lmwh_low: low dose low-molecular-weight heparin; Lmwh_int: Intermediate dose low-molecular-weight heparin; pentasach: pentasaccharides; ufh_low: low dose unfractionated heparin; ufh_int: intermediate dose unfractionated heparin

Figure S13. Within-study bias: serious adverse events

Within-study bias assessment for serious adverse events. The y-axis displays each comparison. The x-axis represents the percentage of studies with respective low risks of bias (green) versus unclear or high risks of bias (red). Doac: direct oral anticoagulants; Lmwh_low: low dose low-molecular-weight heparin; lmwh_int: Intermediate dose low-molecular-weight heparin; pentasach: pentasaccharides; ufh_low: low dose unfractionated heparin; ufh_int: intermediate dose unfractionated heparin

Table S1. PRISMA NMA Checklist of Items

Section/Topic	Item #	Checklist Item	Reported on Page #
TITLE			
Title	1	Identify the report as a systematic review <i>incorporating a network meta-analysis (or related form of meta-analysis)</i> .	1
ABSTRACT			
Structured summary	2	Provide a structured summary including, as applicable: Background: main objectives Methods: data sources; study eligibility criteria, participants, and interventions; study appraisal; and <i>synthesis methods, such as network meta-analysis</i> . Results: number of studies and participants identified; summary estimates with corresponding confidence/credible intervals; <i>treatment rankings may also be discussed. Authors may choose to summarize pairwise comparisons against a chosen treatment included in their analyses for brevity.</i> Discussion/Conclusions: limitations; conclusions and implications of findings. Other: primary source of funding; systematic review registration number with registry me.	2
INTRODUCTION			
Rationale	3	Describe the rationale for the review in the context of what is already known, <i>including mention of why a network meta-analysis has been conducted</i> .	4
Objectives	4	Provide an explicit statement of questions being addressed, with reference to participants, interventions, comparisons, outcomes, and study design (PICOS).	5
METHODS			
Protocol and registration	5	Indicate whether a review protocol exists and if and where it can be accessed (e.g., Web address); and, if available, provide registration information, including registration number.	4
Eligibility criteria	6	Specify study characteristics (e.g., PICOS, length of follow-up) and report characteristics (e.g., years considered, language, publication status) used as criteria for eligibility, giving rationale. <i>Clearly describe eligible treatments included in the treatment network, and note whether any have been clustered or merged into the same node (with justification)</i> .	5
Information sources	7	Describe all information sources (e.g., databases with dates of coverage, contact with study authors to identify additional studies) in the search and date last searched.	5
Search	8	Present full electronic search strategy for at least one database, including any limits used, such that it could be repeated.	5, supplements
Study selection	9	State the process for selecting studies (i.e., screening, eligibility, included in systematic review, and, if applicable, included in the meta-analysis).	5
Data collection process	10	Describe method of data extraction from reports (e.g., piloted forms, independently, in duplicate) and any processes for obtaining and confirming data from investigators.	6
Data items	11	List and define all variables for which data were sought (e.g., PICOS, funding sources) and any assumptions and simplifications made.	5, 6

Table S1. PRISMA NMA Checklist of Items

Geometry of the network	S1	Describe methods used to explore the geometry of the treatment network under study and potential biases related to it. This should include how the evidence base has been graphically summarized for presentation, and what characteristics were compiled and used to describe the evidence base to readers.	9, Fig 1
Risk of bias within individual studies	12	Describe methods used for assessing risk of bias of individual studies (including specification of whether this was done at the study or outcome level), and how this information is to be used in any data synthesis.	6,7
Summary measures	13	State the principal summary measures (e.g., risk ratio, difference in means). <i>Also describe the use of additional summary measures assessed, such as treatment rankings and surface under the cumulative ranking curve (SUCRA) values, as well as modified approaches used to present summary findings from meta-analyses.</i>	7,8
Planned methods of analysis	14	Describe the methods of handling data and combining results of studies for each network meta-analysis. This should include, but not be limited to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Handling of multi-arm trials;</i> • <i>Selection of variance structure;</i> • <i>Selection of prior distributions in Bayesian analyses; and</i> • <i>Assessment of model fit.</i> 	7,8
Assessment of Inconsistency	S2	Describe the statistical methods used to evaluate the agreement of direct and indirect evidence in the treatment network(s) studied. Describe efforts taken to address its presence when found.	8,10, supplements
Risk of bias across studies	15	Specify any assessment of risk of bias that may affect the cumulative evidence (e.g., publication bias, selective reporting within studies).	6,7
Additional analyses	16	Describe methods of additional analyses if done, indicating which were pre-specified. This may include, but not be limited to, the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sensitivity or subgroup analyses; • Meta-regression analyses; • <i>Alternative formulations of the treatment network; and</i> • <i>Use of alternative prior distributions for Bayesian analyses (if applicable).</i> 	8,9
RESULTS†			
Study selection	17	Give numbers of studies screened, assessed for eligibility, and included in the review, with reasons for exclusions at each stage, ideally with a flow diagram.	8,9, supplements
Presentation of network structure	S3	Provide a network graph of the included studies to enable visualization of the geometry of the treatment network.	Fig 1
Summary of network geometry	S4	Provide a brief overview of characteristics of the treatment network. This may include commentary on the abundance of trials and randomized patients for the different interventions and pairwise comparisons in the network, gaps of evidence in the treatment network, and potential biases reflected by the network structure.	8,9
Study characteristics	18	For each study, present characteristics for which data were extracted (e.g., study size, PICOS, follow-up period) and provide the citations.	Supplements
Risk of bias within studies	19	Present data on risk of bias of each study and, if available, any outcome level assessment.	Supplements

Table S1. PRISMA NMA Checklist of Items

Results of individual studies	20	For all outcomes considered (benefits or harms), present, for each study: 1) simple summary data for each intervention group, and 2) effect estimates and confidence intervals. <i>Modified approaches may be needed to deal with information from larger networks.</i>	11,12
Synthesis of results	21	Present results of each meta-analysis done, including confidence/credible intervals. <i>In larger networks, authors may focus on comparisons versus a particular comparator (e.g. placebo or standard care), with full findings presented in an appendix. League tables and forest plots may be considered to summarize pairwise comparisons.</i> If additional summary measures were explored (such as treatment rankings), these should also be presented.	11,12
Exploration for inconsistency	S5	Describe results from investigations of inconsistency. This may include such information as measures of model fit to compare consistency and inconsistency models, <i>P</i> values from statistical tests, or summary of inconsistency estimates from different parts of the treatment network.	10, supplements
Risk of bias across studies	22	Present results of any assessment of risk of bias across studies for the evidence base being studied.	9,10, supplements
Results of additional analyses	23	Give results of additional analyses, if done (e.g., sensitivity or subgroup analyses, meta-regression analyses, <i>alternative network geometries studied, alternative choice of prior distributions for Bayesian analyses, and so forth</i>).	12
DISCUSSION			
Summary of evidence	24	Summarize the main findings, including the strength of evidence for each main outcome; consider their relevance to key groups (e.g., healthcare providers, users, and policy-makers).	12-15
Limitations	25	Discuss limitations at study and outcome level (e.g., risk of bias), and at review level (e.g., incomplete retrieval of identified research, reporting bias). <i>Comment on the validity of the assumptions, such as transitivity and consistency. Comment on any concerns regarding network geometry (e.g., avoidance of certain comparisons).</i>	13,14
Conclusions	26	Provide a general interpretation of the results in the context of other evidence, and implications for future research.	12-15
FUNDING			
Funding	27	Describe sources of funding for the systematic review and other support (e.g., supply of data); role of funders for the systematic review. This should also include information regarding whether funding has been received from manufacturers of treatments in the network and/or whether some of the authors are content experts with professional conflicts of interest that could affect use of treatments in the network.	18

PICOS = population, intervention, comparators, outcomes, study design.

* Text in italics indicates wording specific to reporting of network meta-analyses that has been added to guidance from the PRISMA statement.

† Authors may wish to plan for use of appendices to present all relevant information in full detail for items in this section.

Table S2. Search Strategy

PubMed
<p>("Heparin, Low-Molecular-Weight"[Mesh] OR ((low-molecular-weight[tiab] OR unfractionated[tiab]) AND heparin*[tiab]) OR lmwh[tiab] OR nadroparin*[tiab] OR fraxiparin*[tiab] OR cy 216[tiab] OR cy216[tiab] OR lmf cy216[tiab] OR seleparin*[tiab] OR enoxaparin*[tiab] OR clexane[tiab] OR klexane[tiab] OR lovenox[tiab] OR emt 966[tiab] OR emt 967[tiab] OR pk-10,169[tiab] OR pk 10169[tiab] OR pk10169[tiab] OR dalteparin*[tiab] OR fragmin*[tiab] OR tedelparin[tiab] OR kabi 2165[tiab] OR fr 860[tiab] OR tinzaparin*[tiab] OR innohep[tiab] OR logiparin[tiab] OR lhn-1[tiab] OR ardeparin*[tiab] OR normiflo[tiab] OR bemiparin*[tiab] OR zibor*[tiab] OR certoparin*[tiab] OR mono-emborex[tiab] OR emborex[tiab] OR sandoparin[tiab] OR cy222 OR cy 222 OR reviparin*[tiab] OR clivarin[tiab] OR lu 47311[tiab] OR parnaparin[tiab] OR cb-01-05-mmx[tiab] OR fluxum[tiab] OR semuloparin*[tiab] OR ave5026[tiab] OR fondaparinux[tiab] OR ldraparinux[tiab] OR idrabiotaparinux[tiab] OR "Anticoagulants"[Mesh] OR anticoagul*[tiab] OR thrombin inhibitor*[tiab] OR "Factor Xa Inhibitors" [Pharmacological Action] OR factor Xa inhibitor*[tiab] OR rivaroxaban[tiab] OR xarelto[tiab] OR edoxaban[tiab] OR lixiana[tiab] OR apixaban[tiab] OR eliquis[tiab] OR betrixaban[tiab] OR dabigatran[tiab] OR pradaxa[tiab] OR NOAC*[tiab] OR DOAC*[tiab] OR "Coumarins"[Mesh] OR sintrom[tiab] OR warfarin[tiab] OR coumarin*[tiab] OR marcoumar[tiab] OR marcumar[tiab] OR phenprocoum*[tiab]) AND ("Thrombosis"[Mesh] OR thrombos*[tiab] OR thrombot*[tiab] OR "Thromboembolism"[Mesh] OR thromboembol*[tiab] OR thrombo-prophyla*[tiab] OR thromboprophyla*[tiab] OR "Pulmonary Embolism"[Mesh] OR vte[tiab] OR dvt[tiab]) AND (randomized controlled trial[pt] OR ("Clinical Trial" [Publication Type] OR "Clinical Trials as Topic"[Mesh]) AND "Random Allocation"[Mesh]) OR randomi*[tiab] OR randomly[tiab] OR placebo[tiab] OR trial[ti]) NOT ((animals[mh] NOT humans[mh]) OR "Review" [Publication Type]) NOT (atrial fibrillation[ti] OR coronary[ti] OR pregnan*[ti] OR eclamp*[ti] OR fetal[ti] OR stent thrombosis[tiab] OR revascularization[tiab] OR restenosis[tiab] OR stent implantation[tiab] OR pci[tiab] OR primary pci[tiab] OR stent[tiab] OR stents[tiab] OR stenting[tiab] OR stenosis[tiab] OR primary percutaneous coronary[tiab] OR st segment elevation[tiab] OR occlusion[tiab] OR implantation[tiab] OR unstable angina[tiab] OR stemi[tiab])</p>
EMBASE
<p>('low molecular weight heparin'/exp OR 'heparin'/exp OR 'heparin derivative'/exp OR (unfractionated AND heparin) OR (lmwh OR nadroparin* OR fraxiparin* OR 'cy 216' OR cy216 OR 'lmf cy216' OR seleparin* OR enoxaparin* OR clexane OR klexane OR lovenox OR 'emt 966' OR 'emt 967' OR 'pk-10,169' OR 'pk 10169' OR pk10169 OR dalteparin* OR fragmin* OR tedelparin OR 'kabi 2165' OR 'fr 860' OR tinzaparin* OR innohep OR logiparin OR 'lhn-1' OR ardeparin* OR normiflo OR bemiparin* OR zibor* OR certoparin* OR mono-emborex OR emborex OR sandoparin OR cy222 OR 'cy 222' OR reviparin* OR clivarin OR 'lu 47311' OR parnaparin OR cb-01-05-mmx OR fluxum OR semuloparin* OR ave5026):ab,ti OR 'anticoagulant agent' OR (fondaparinux OR ldraparinux OR idrabiotaparinux):ab,ti OR 'apixaban'/exp OR 'betrixaban'/exp OR 'edoxaban'/exp OR 'rivaroxaban'/exp OR 'dabigatran'/exp OR (apixaban OR betrixaban OR edoxaban OR rivaroxaban OR dabigatran OR noac* OR doac* OR lixiana OR pradaxa OR eliquis OR xarelto):ab,ti OR 'coumarin anticoagulant'/exp OR (sintrom OR warfarin OR coumarin* OR marcoumar OR marcumar OR phenprocoum*):ab,ti) AND ('thromboembolism'/exp OR (thrombos* OR thrombot* OR thromboembol* OR thrombo-prophyla* OR thromboprophyla* OR 'pulmonary embolism' OR dvt OR vte):ab,ti) AND ('randomized controlled trial'/exp OR (randomi*ed NEXT/3 controlled NEXT/3 (trial OR study)):ab,ti OR trial:ti) NOT ('animal'/exp OR 'nonhuman'/exp NOT 'human'/exp) NOT (('atrial fibrillation' OR coronar* OR pregnan* OR eclamp* OR fetal):ti) NOT ('stent thrombosis' OR revascularization OR restenosis OR 'stent implantation' OR pci OR 'primary pci' OR stent OR stents OR stenting OR stenosis OR 'primary percutaneous coronary' OR 'st segment elevation' OR occlusion OR implantation OR 'unstable angina' OR stemi):ab,ti</p>

Table S2. Search Strategy

<p>Web of Science</p> <p>(TS=(Low-molecular-weight heparin* OR lmwh OR heparin OR "unfractionated heparin" OR nadroparin* OR fraxiparin* OR cy216 OR "cy 216" OR "lmf cy216" OR seleparin* OR tedegliparin* OR enoxaparin* OR clexane OR klexane OR lovenox OR emt966 OR "emt 966" OR "emt 967" OR "pk-10,169" OR "pk 10169" OR pk10169 OR dalteparin* OR fragmin* OR tedelparin OR kabi2165 OR"kabi 2165" OR fr 860 OR fr860 OR tinzaparin* OR innohep OR logiparin OR "lhn-1" OR ardeparin OR normiflo OR bemiparin OR zibor OR certoparin OR alphaparin OR "mono-embolex" OR embolex OR sandoparin OR cy222 OR "cy 222" OR reviparin* OR clivarin OR "lu-47311" OR parnaparin OR "cb-01-05-mmx" OR fluxum OR semuloparin OR ave5026) OR TS=(fondaparinux OR ldraparinux OR idrabiotaparinux) OR TS=(apixaban OR betrixaban OR edoxaban OR rivaroxaban OR dabigatran OR noac* OR doac* OR lixiana OR pradaxa OR eliquis OR xarelto) OR TS=(sintrom OR warfarin OR coumarin* OR marcoumar OR marcumar OR phenprocoum*)) AND (TS=(thrombos* OR thromboembol* OR thrombot* OR thrombo-prophyla* OR thromboprophyla* OR pulmonary embolism OR vte OR dvt)) AND (TS=random*) NOT (TI=("atrial fibrillation" OR coronar* OR pregnan* OR eclamp* OR fetal)) NOT (TS=("stent thrombosis" OR revascularization OR restenosis OR "stent implantation" OR pci OR "primary pci" OR stent OR stents OR stenting OR stenosis OR "primary percutaneous coronary" OR "st segment elevation" OR occlusion OR implantation OR "unstable angina" OR stemi))</p>
<p>Cochrane (search in: trials)</p> <p>(Low-molecular-weight heparin* OR lmwh OR heparin OR "unfractionated heparin" OR nadroparin* OR fraxiparin* OR cy216 OR "cy 216" OR "lmf cy216" OR seleparin* OR tedegliparin* OR enoxaparin* OR clexane OR klexane OR lovenox OR emt966 OR "emt 966" OR "emt 967" OR "pk-10,169" OR "pk 10169" OR pk10169 OR dalteparin* OR fragmin* OR tedelparin OR kabi2165 OR"kabi 2165" OR fr 860 OR fr860 OR tinzaparin* OR innohep OR logiparin OR "lhn-1" OR ardeparin OR normiflo OR bemiparin OR zibor OR certoparin OR alphaparin OR "mono-embolex" OR embolex OR sandoparin OR cy222 OR "cy 222" OR reviparin* OR clivarin OR "lu-47311" OR parnaparin OR "cb 01 05 mmx" OR fluxum OR semuloparin OR ave5026 OR fondaparinux OR ldraparinux OR idrabiotaparinux OR apixaban OR betrixaban OR edoxaban OR rivaroxaban OR dabigatran OR noac* OR doac* OR lixiana OR pradaxa OR eliquis OR Xarelto OR sintrom OR warfarin OR coumarin* OR marcoumar OR marcumar OR phenprocoum*):ti,ab,kw AND (thrombos* OR thromboembol* OR thrombot* OR "thrombo-prophyla*" OR thromboprophyla* OR pulmonary embolism OR vte OR dvt):ti,ab,kw NOT ("atrial fibrillation" OR coronar* OR pregnan* OR eclamp* OR fetal):ti</p>

Table S3. Prior distributions**Prior distributions for between-trial standard deviation in the main analyses:**

Mortality:	U(0, 2)
VTE:	U(0, 1.95)
Major bleeding:	U(0, 2.2)
SAE:	U(0, 1.06)

Prior distributions for trial baselines and effect estimates in the main analyses:

Mortality:	N(0, 0.001)
VTE:	N(0, 0.001)
Bleeding:	N(0, 0.0009)
SAE:	N(0, 0.004)

We conducted two sensitivity analyses. In sensitivity analysis 4.1 we assumed an even more ‘uninformative’ heterogeneity prior distribution. In sensitivity analysis 4.2 we assumed an empirical heterogeneity prior distribution based on data as proposed by Turner et al [4].

Prior distributions for between-trial standard deviation in sensitivity analysis 4.1

Mortality:	U(0, 5)
VTE:	U(0, 5)
Major bleeding:	U(0, 5)
SAE:	U(0, 5)

Prior distributions for between-trial standard deviation in sensitivity analysis 4.2

Mortality:	Log-normal (-4.27,1.48 ²): median = 0.014; 95% range = (0.0008–0.25)
VTE:	Log-normal (-3.23,1.88 ²): median = 0.040; 95% range = (0.001–1.58)
Major bleeding:	Log-normal (-3.23,1.88 ²): median = 0.040; 95% range = (0.001–1.58)
SAE:	Log-normal (-3.23,1.88 ²): median = 0.040; 95% range = (0.001–1.58)

Table S4. List of 18 eligible RCTs, excluded based on interventions

STUDY	SETTING			REASON FOR EXCLUSION
	Year	Population	n	
AUTHOR				
ELIAS [5]	1990	stroke	30	Unable to classify LMWH dose
TAKKUNER [6]	1996	critically ill	66	Intermediate vs intermediate dose LMWH
COHN [7]	1999	trauma	104	Unable to classify LMWH dose
CHIOU-TAN [8]	2003	trauma	95	Intermediate vs intermediate dose LMWH
NCT00714597 [9]	2012	medical	421	Unable to classify LMWH dose
ROBINSON [10]	2013	critically ill	80	Intermediate vs intermediate dose LMWH
LI [11]	2015	critically ill	36	Unable to classify LMWH dose
ABBAS [12]	2017	critically ill	100	Intermediate vs intermediate dose LMWH
ZWICKER [13]	2019	medical	47	Intermediate vs intermediate dose LMWH
CHAMOON [14]	2019	medical	32	Low vs low dose LMWH
HESACOVID [15]	2020	COVID-19	20	Intermediate vs intermediate dose LMWH
REMAP-CAP, ACTIV-4A, ATTACC MULTIPLATFORM TRIAL [16]	2021	COVID-19 (ward)	2219	Intervention was a mix of LMWH and UFH
REMAP-CAP, ACTIV-4A, ATTACC MULTIPLATFORM TRIAL [17]	2021	COVID-19 (ICU)	1098	Intervention was a mix of LMWH and UFH
ACTION [18]	2021	COVID-19	615	Intervention was a mix of DOAC, LMWH and UFH
PEREPU [19]	2021	COVID-19	176	Intermediate vs intermediate dose LMWH
INSPIRATION [20]	2021	COVID-19	600	Intermediate vs intermediate dose LMWH
RAPID [21]	2021	COVID-19	465	Intervention was a mix of LMWH and UFH
HEP-COVID [22]	2021	COVID-19	257	Intervention was a mix of LMWH and UFH

Table S5. List of 16 RCTs, excluded based on transitivity considerations

STUDY AUTHOR	SETTING			Country (n)	Population	Age	Female (%)	TREATMENT				CO-INTERVENTION			MORTALITY		VTE		BLEEDING		SAE	
	Year	Arms (n)	Setup					Drug	Dose	Freq	Drug class	Duration (days)	TAI (%)	Mech (%)	Patients	Events	Total	Events	Total	Events	Total	Events
PETERS [23]	1982	2	S	1	cardiology	64	27	indobufen	200mg	2	tar	10			74	6	74	0	74	0	74	
								acenocoumarol			10			76	10	76	0	76	2	76		
TURPIE [24]	1987	2	M	1	stroke	69	47	org 10172	750iu	2	heparinoid	12	0	0	50	4	50	0	50	1	50	
								placebo		2	placebo	14	0	0	25	5	25	2	25	0	25	
GREEN [25]	1990	2	S	1	trauma	30	17	tinzaparin	3500iu	1	LMWH (low)	47	0	0	20			0	20	0	20	
								UFH	5000iu	3	UFH (int)	40	0	0	21			3	21	2	21	
TURPIE [26]	1992	2	M	1	stroke	72	56	org 10172	750iu	2	heparinoid	12	0	0	45	9	45			1	45	
								UFH	5000iu	2	UFH (low)	12	0	0	42	9	42			0	42	
DUMAS [27]	1994	2	M	4	stroke	73	58	org 10172	1250iu	1	heparinoid	9	0	0	89	17	89			2	89	
								UFH	5000iu	2	UFH (low)	9	0	0	90	11	86			1	86	
BERGQVIST [28]	1996	2	M	1	surgery	70	54	tinzaparin	3500iu	1	LMWH (low)	5			39	0	39	0	39	1	39	
								placebo		1	placebo	5			41	2	41	1	41	0	41	
GEERTS [29]	1996	2	S	1	trauma	38	28	enoxaparin	30mg	2	LMWH (int)	14	0	0	171			1	171	5	171	
								UFH	5000iu	2	UFH (low)	14	0	0	173			0	173	1	173	
CHEN [30]	1997	2	M	1	stroke	63	37	placebo		1	placebo	28			10552	398	10320	20	10320	151	10320	
								aspirin	160mg	1	tar	28	100	100	10554	343	10335	12	10335	201	10335	
BATH [31]	2001	3	M	10	stroke		45	tinzaparin	WB*	1	LMWH (int)	10	0	0	508	28	507	6	507	5	507	
								aspirin	150mg	2	tar	10	100	100	491	17	491	13	491	3	491	
LOHMANN [32]	2001	2	S	1	trauma	35	17	dalteparin	5000iu	1	LMWH (int)	46	0	0	80			6	80	0	80	
								UFH	7500iu	2	UFH (int)	54	0	0	86			12	86	0	86	
AGARWAL [33]	2009	2	S	1	trauma	32	20	none			none				131			4	131			
								UFH	5000iu	2	UFH (low)	90			166			3	166			
HALIM [34]	2014	2	S	1	trauma	34	19	none			none		100	37			2	37				
								enoxaparin	40mg	1	LMWH (int)	56			100	37			2	37		
OLSON [35]	2015	2	S	1	trauma	46	72	enoxaparin	30mg	2	LMWH (int)	7		100	30	1	216	0	216	4	216	
								UFH	5000iu	3	UFH (int)	7		100	30	2	220	1	220	0	220	
AHUJA [36,36]	2016	2	S	1	burns	29	43	none			none		0	50	7	50	4	50	0	50		
								enoxaparin	WB*	2	LMWH (int)	14		0	50	8	50	0	50	0	50	
PIRAN [37]	2019	2	S	1	trauma	61	12	dalteparin	5000iu	1	LMWH (int)	90			4			0	4	0	4	
								apixaban	2,5mg	2	doac	90			4			0	4	1	4	0
PACIARONI [38]	2020	2	M	1	stroke (haemorrhage)	71	45	none			none	10		43	35	6	35	3	35	3	35	
								enoxaparin	40mg	1	LMWH (int)	10		53	38	7	38	0	38	1	38	1

Study-level characteristics that were judged to threaten transitivity and that formed the basis for exclusion, are bold and underscored. *Weight-based, Bath 2001: 100 aXa IU/kg; Ahuja 2016: 0,5mg/kg (max daily 60mg). DOAC: Direct Acting Oral Anticoagulant; int: intermediate dose; IU: international units; LMWH: Low-Molecular-Weight heparin; low: low dose; M: multicenter; mech: mechanical prophylaxis including compression stockings and intermittent pneumatic compression devices; S: single-center; SAE: serious adverse events; TAI: thrombocyte aggregation inhibitors; UFH: Unfractionated Heparin; VTE: venous thromboembolism.

Table S6. Characteristics of 44 RCTs included in main analysis

STUDY Author	SETTING				TREATMENT							CO-INTERVENTION				MORTALITY		VTE		BLEEDING		SAE		
	Year	Arms (n)	Setup	Country (n)	Population	Age	Female (%)	Drug	Dose	Freq	Drug Class	Duration (Days)	TAI (%)	Mech (%)	Patients	Events	Total	Events	Total	Events	Total	Events	Total	
WARLOW [39]	1973	2	S	1	cardiology	NR	NR	placebo UFH	5000iu	2 2	placebo UFH (low)	10 10	NR NR	NR NR	73 73	5 6	64 63	4 1	64 63	0 0	64 63	NR NR	NR NR	
PRANDONI [40]	1986	2	S	1	cardiology	57	9	placebo UFH	5000iu	3 3	placebo UFH (int)	7 7	0 0	NR NR	37 38	NR NR	NR NR	0 0	27 33	NR NR	NR NR	NR NR	NR NR	
ZAWILSKA [41]	1989	2	S	1	cardiology	58	23	none UFH	5000iu	2	none UFH (low)	21	NR NR	NR NR	53 50	6 5	53 50	3 0	53 50	0 0	53 50	NR NR	NR NR	
MCCARTHY [42]	1977	2	S	1	stroke	78	66	none UFH	5000iu	3	UFH (int)	14	NR NR	NR NR	16 16	5 3	16 16	NR NR	NR NR	NR NR	NR NR	NR NR	NR NR	
MCCARTHY [43]	1986	2	M	1	stroke	76	57	none UFH	5000iu	3	UFH (int)	14	NR NR	NR NR	161 144	53 31	161 144	33 7	161 144	NR NR	NR NR	NR NR	NR NR	
DICKMANN [44]	1988	2	S	1	stroke	61	50	none UFH	5000iu	3	UFH (int)	6	NR NR	NR NR	23 23	4 5	23 23	NR NR	NR NR	NR NR	NR NR	NR NR	NR NR	
PRINS [45]	1989	2	S	1	stroke	NR	48	placebo dalteparin	2500iu	2 2	placebo LMWH (int)	14 14	0 0	NR NR	30 30	4 9	30 30	NR NR	NR NR	NR NR	NR NR	27 22	NR NR	NR NR
SANDSET [46]	1990	2	S	1	stroke	NR	55	placebo dalteparin	3000- 5500iu	1 1	placebo LMWH (low)	14 14	NR NR	NR NR	51 52	1 5	51 52	1 0	50 42	0 0	51 52	NR NR	NR NR	
KAY [47]	1995	3	M	1	stroke	67	42	placebo nadroparin nadroparin	4100iu 4100iu	1 1 2	placebo LMWH (low) LMWH (int)	10 10 10	NR NR NR	NR NR NR	105 102 105	8 8 7	105 101 102	1 0 0	105 101 102	NR NR NR	NR NR NR	NR NR NR	NR NR NR	
IST [48]	1997	6	M	36	stroke	72	46	none UFH	5000iu	2	UFH (low)	14	53 52	NR NR	9718 4861	905 424	9717 4860	98 37	9717 4860	77 64	9717 4860	NR NR	NR NR	
DIENER [49]	2001	4	M	1	stroke	66	43	UFH certoparin certoparin	12500iu 3000iu 3000iu	2 1 2	UFH (int) LMWH (low) LMWH (int)	14 12 12	52 NR NR	NR NR NR	4856 99 102	452 3 0	4856 99 102	21 0 1	4856 99 102	180 3 1	4856 99 102	NR NR NR	NR NR NR	
HILLBOM [50]	2002	2	M	1	stroke	68	40	enoxaparin UFH	40mg 5000iu	1 3	LMWH (int) UFH (int)	10 10	0 0	NR NR	106 106	21 28	106 106	2 5	106 106	1 0	106 106	NR NR	NR NR	
DIENER [51]	2006	2	M	3	stroke	67	43	certoparin UFH	3000iu 5000iu	1 3	LMWH (low) UFH (int)	14 14	NR NR	NR NR	272 273	14 8	272 273	1 0	272 273	3 5	272 273	NR NR	NR NR	
SHERMAN [52]	2007	2	M	15	stroke	66	44	UFH enoxaparin	5000iu 40mg	2 1	UFH (low) LMWH (int)	10 10	90 92	NR NR	878 884	103 100	872 877	11 5	669 666	6 11	872 877	NR NR	NR NR	
BELCH [53]	1981	2	S	1	medical	66	31	none UFH	5000iu	3	UFH (int)	NR	NR NR	NR NR	50 50	NR NR	NR NR	2 0	50 50	0 0	50 50	NR NR	NR NR	
DAHAN [54]	1986	2	S	1	medical	80	38	enoxaparin placebo	60mg NR	1 1	LMWH (int) placebo	10 10	0 0	NR NR	135 135	6 6	132 131	1 3	132 131	NR NR	NR NR	NR NR	NR NR	
PONIEWIERSKI [55]	1988	2	S	1	medical	59	39	UFH dalteparin	5000iu 2500iu	2 1	UFH (low) LMWH (low)	10 10	NR NR	NR NR	100 100	NR NR	NR NR	0 1	89 92	0 0	89 92	NR NR	NR NR	
AQUINO [1]	1990	2	S	1	medical	84	86	nadroparin UFH	2850iu WB *	1 2	LMWH (low) UFH (low)	NR NR	NR NR	NR NR	49 50	1 2	49 50	1 1	49 50	0 2	49 50	NR NR	NR NR	
HARENBERG [56]	1990	2	S	1	medical	66	55	UFH dalteparin	5000iu 1500iu	3 1	UFH (int) LMWH (low)	10 10	0 0	0 0	100 100	1 3	82 84	0 1	82 84	NR NR	NR NR	NR NR	NR NR	
FORETTE [2]	1995	2	M	1	medical	83	75	nadroparin UFH	3075iu WB *	1 2	LMWH (low) UFH (low)	28 28	0 0	NR NR	146 149	6 7	146 149	0 2	146 149	0 4	146 149	NR NR	NR NR	
BERGMANN [3]	1996	2	M	1	medical	83	72	enoxaparin UFH	20mg 5000iu	1 2	LMWH (low) UFH (low)	10 10	0 0	NR NR	217 225	7 8	216 223	1 0	207 216	1 2	216 223	1 2	216 223	NR NR
GARDLUND [57]	1996	2	M	1	medical	75	NR	none UFH	5000iu	2	UFH (low)	8	NR	NR	5917 5776	333 304	5917 5776	84 62	5917 5776	6 14	5917 5776	NR NR	NR NR	
HARENBERG [58]	1996	2	M	1	medical	70	55	nadroparin UFH	36mg 5000iu	1 3	LMWH (low) UFH (int)	10 10	NR NR	NR NR	983 985	23 9	810 780	2 3	810 780	5 4	810 780	NR NR	NR NR	
LECHLER [59]	1996	2	M	2	medical	74	62	enoxaparin UFH	40mg 5000iu	1 3	LMWH (int) UFH (int)	7 7	0 0	NR NR	477 482	7 11	477 482	1 4	442 443	2 7	477 482	NR NR	NR NR	
SAMAMA [60]	1999	3	M	9	medical	73	50	placebo enoxaparin enoxaparin	NR 20mg 40mg	1 1 1	placebo LMWH (low) LMWH (int)	7 7 7	NR NR NR	NR NR NR	371 364 367	50 51 41	362 351 360	8 8 5	263 263 272	7 4 12	362 351 360	NR NR NR	NR NR NR	
KLEBER [61]	2003	2	M	1	medical	70	48	enoxaparin UFH	40mg 5000iu	1 3	LMWH (int) UFH (int)	10 10	NR NR	NR NR	20 20	332 333	1 15	332 333	1 1	239 212	1 1	332 333	8 23	332 333
LEIZOROVICZ [62]	2004	2	M	26	medical	68	52	dalteparin placebo	5000iu	1 1	LMWH (int) placebo	14 14	NR NR	NR NR	1856 1850	107 103	1747 1715	15 21	1615 1583	9 3	1829 1807	NR NR	NR NR	
MAHE [63]	2005	2	M	4	medical	76	NR	nadroparin placebo	2850iu	1 1	LMWH (low) placebo	13 13	0 0	NR NR	1230 1244	124 128	1230 1244	29 38	1230 1244	1 3	1230 1244	NR NR	NR NR	

Table S6. Characteristics of 44 RCTs included in main analysis

COHEN [64]	2006	2	M	8	medical	75	58	fondaparinux	2,5mg	1	pentasach	7	NR	NR	429	14	425	4	429	1	425	NR	NR
								placebo	NR	1	placebo	7	NR	NR	420	25	414	11	420	1	414	NR	NR
LEDERLE [65]	2006	2	M	1	medical	72	1	enoxaparin	40mg	1	LMWH (int)	13	NR	NR	140	13	140	5	140	2	140	NR	NR
								placebo		1	placebo	11	NR	NR	140	14	140	9	140	5	140	NR	NR
NCT00445328 [66]	2009	2	M	1	medical	61	47	dalteparin	5000iu	1	LMWH (int)	6	NR	NR	42	0	37	0	37	0	37	2	41
								UFH	5000iu	3	UFH (int)	6	NR	NR	42	1	37	0	37	1	37	4	42
RIESS [67]	2010	2	M	2	medical	79	59	certoparin	3000iu	1	LMWH (low)	9	52	NR	1626	86	1624	16	1483	7	1624	203	1624
								UFH	5000iu	3	UFH (int)	9	52	NR	1618	93	1615	13	1454	10	1615	222	1615
SCHELLONG [68]	2010	2	M	1	medical	71	52	certoparin	3000iu	1	LMWH (low)	8	NR	NR	163	9	150	3	150	1	163	20	150
								UFH	7500iu	2	UFH (int)	8	NR	NR	174	15	152	3	152	4	172	30	152
GOLDHABER [69]	2011	2	M	35	medical	67	51	enoxaparin	40mg	1	LMWH (int)	7	NR	NR	3273	NR	NR	7	3273	4	3210	NR	NR
								apixaban	2,5mg	2	doac	25	NR	NR	3255	NR	NR	4	3255	8	3181	NR	NR
KAKKAR [70]	2011	2	M	7	medical	65	37	enoxaparin	40mg	1	LMWH (int)	6	NR	100	4174	348	4171	8	4072	16	4171	243	4171
								placebo		1	placebo	6	NR	100	4145	355	4136	4	4044	11	4136	219	4136
COHEN [71]	2013	2	M	52	medical	71	46	enoxaparin	40mg	1	LMWH (int)	10	NR	0	4051	65	3310	12	4001	11	4001	NR	NR
								rivaroxaban	10mg	1	doac	35	NR	0	4050	72	3218	18	3997	24	3997	NR	NR
COHEN [72]	2016	2	M	35	medical	76	54	enoxaparin	40mg	1	LMWH (int)	9	NR	NR	3754	NR	NR	7	3720	9	3716	NR	NR
								betrixaban	80mg	1	doac	36	NR	NR	3759	NR	NR	5	3721	9	3716	NR	NR
KAPOOR [73]	1999	2	S	1	critically ill	NR	NR	placebo	NR	2	placebo	NR	NR	NR	390	NR	NR	20	390	NR	NR	NR	NR
								UFH	5000iu	2	UFH (low)	NR	NR	NR	401	NR	NR	9	401	NR	NR	NR	NR
GOLDHABER [74]	2000	2	M	NR	critically ill	NR	NR	enoxaparin	30mg	2	LMWH (int)	14	NR	100	156	1	156	NR	NR	3	156	NR	NR
								UFH	5000iu	2	UFH (low)	14	NR	100	154	8	154	NR	NR	3	154	NR	NR
FRAISSE [75]	2000	2	M	1	critically ill	68	22	nadroparin	3800-5700iu	1	LMWH (low)	12	0	NR	109	8	108	0	84	6	108	27	108
								placebo		1	placebo	11	0	NR	114	8	113	0	85	3	113	22	113
LEVI [76]	2007	3	M	20	critically ill	59	41	placebo		2	placebo	4	NR	58	990	NR	NR	46	959	NR	NR	NR	NR
								UFH	5000iu	2	UFH (low)	4	NR	56	511	NR	NR	24	498	NR	NR	NR	NR
								enoxaparin	40mg	1	LMWH (int)	4	NR	56	493	NR	NR	19	478	NR	NR	NR	NR
DE [77]	2010	2	S	1	critically ill	60	25	enoxaparin	40mg	1	LMWH (int)	6	0	0	81	9	81	NR	NR	1	81	NR	NR
								UFH	5000iu	2	UFH (low)	6	0	0	75	6	75	NR	NR	2	75	NR	NR
COOK [78]	2011	2	M	6	critically ill	61	43	dalteparin	5000iu	1	LMWH (int)	7	37	33	1880	414	1873	18	1873	103	1873	7	1873
								UFH	5000iu	2	UFH (low)	7	38	32	1884	459	1873	28	1873	105	1873	6	1873
ISHI [79]	2013	2	S	1	critically ill	54	40	enoxaparin	40mg	1	LMWH (int)	3	NR	NR	44	NR	NR	NR	NR	0	44	NR	NR
								UFH	5000iu	2	UFH (low)	3	NR	NR	48	NR	NR	NR	NR	4	48	NR	NR

*Weight-based, Aquino 1990: 5000IU (< 60kg) / 7500IU (> 60kg), Forette 1995: 5000IU (< 70kg) / 7500IU (>70kg). DOAC: Direct Acting Oral Anticoagulant; int: intermediate dose; IU: international units; LMWH: Low-Molecular-Weight heparin; low: low dose; M: multicenter; mech: mechanical prophylaxis including compression stockings and intermittent pneumatic compression devices; NR: not reported; S: single-center; SAE: serious adverse events; TAI: thrombocyte aggregation inhibitors; UFH: Unfractionated Heparin; VTE: venous thromboembolism.

Table S7. Bias assessment of 44 RCTs included in main analysis

Author	Year	Outcome	Bias arising from randomisation process	Bias due to deviations from interventions	Bias from missing outcome data	Bias in measurement of the outcome	Bias in selection of the reported results	Overall bias judgement	Risk of vested interests
AQUINO	1990	Mortality	Some concerns	Some concerns	Low	Some concerns	Low	High risk	Unclear or high risk
		VTE	Some concerns	Some concerns	Low	Some concerns	Low	High risk	Unclear or high risk
		Major bleeding	Some concerns	Some concerns	Low	Some concerns	Low	High risk	Unclear or high risk
BELCH	1981	VTE	Some concerns	Some concerns	Low	Some concerns	Some concerns	High risk	Unclear or high risk
		Major bleeding	Some concerns	Some concerns	Low	Some concerns	Some concerns	High risk	Unclear or high risk
BERGMANN	1996	Mortality	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low risk	Unclear or high risk
		VTE	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low risk	Unclear or high risk
		Major bleeding	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low risk	Unclear or high risk
		SAE	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low risk	Unclear or high risk
COHEN	2006	Mortality	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low risk	Unclear or high risk
		VTE	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low risk	Unclear or high risk
		Major bleeding	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low risk	Unclear or high risk
COHEN	2013	Mortality	Low	High	Some concerns	Low	Low	High risk	Unclear or high risk
		VTE	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	High risk	Unclear or high risk
		Major bleeding	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	High risk	Unclear or high risk
COHEN	2016	VTE	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low risk	Unclear or high risk
		Major bleeding	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low risk	Unclear or high risk
COOK	2011	Mortality	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low risk	Low risk
		VTE	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low risk	Low risk
		Major bleeding	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low risk	Low risk
		SAE	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low risk	Low risk
DAHAN	1986	Mortality	Some concerns	Low	Low	Low	Some concerns	High risk	Low risk
		VTE	Some concerns	Low	Low	Low	Some concerns	High risk	Low risk
DE	2010	Mortality	High	High	High	Low	Some concerns	High risk	Unclear or high risk
		Major bleeding	High	High	High	Low	Some concerns	High risk	Unclear or high risk
DICKMANN	1988	Mortality	Some concerns	Some concerns	Low	Low	Some concerns	High risk	Low risk
DIENER	2001	Mortality	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low risk	Unclear or high risk
		VTE	Low	Low	Low	Some concerns	Low	High risk	Unclear or high risk
		Major bleeding	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low risk	Unclear or high risk
DIENER	2006	Mortality	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low risk	Unclear or high risk
		VTE	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low risk	Unclear or high risk
		Major bleeding	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low risk	Unclear or high risk
FORETTE	1995	Mortality	Low	Some concerns	Low	Low	Low	High risk	Unclear or high risk
		VTE	Low	Some concerns	Low	Some concerns	Low	High risk	Unclear or high risk
		Major bleeding	Low	Some concerns	Low	Some concerns	Low	High risk	Unclear or high risk
FRAISSE	2000	Mortality	High	Low	Low	Low	Low	High risk	Unclear or high risk
		VTE	High	High	Some concerns	Low	Low	High risk	Unclear or high risk
		Major bleeding	High	Low	Low	Low	Low	High risk	Unclear or high risk
		SAE	High	Low	Low	Low	Low	High risk	Unclear or high risk
GARDLUND	1996	Mortality	Some concerns	Some concerns	Low	Low	Low	High risk	Unclear or high risk
		VTE	Some concerns	Some concerns	Some concerns	Low	Low	High risk	Unclear or high risk
		Major bleeding	Some concerns	Some concerns	Some concerns	Low	Low	High risk	Unclear or high risk
GOLDHABER	2000	Mortality	Some concerns	Some concerns	Some concerns	Some concerns	Some concerns	High risk	Unclear or high risk
		Major bleeding	Some concerns	Some concerns	Some concerns	Some concerns	Some concerns	High risk	Unclear or high risk
GOLDHABER	2011	VTE	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low risk	Unclear or high risk

Table S7. Bias assessment of 44 RCTs included in main analysis

Author	Year	Outcome	Bias arising from randomisation process	Bias due to deviations from interventions	Bias from missing outcome data	Bias in measurement of the outcome	Bias in selection of the reported results	Overall bias judgement	Risk of vested interests
HARENBERG	1990	Major bleeding	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low risk	Unclear or high risk
		Mortality	Some concerns	Some concerns	Low	Low	Some concerns	High risk	Unclear or high risk
		VTE	Some concerns	Some concerns	Low	Some concerns	Some concerns	High risk	Unclear or high risk
HARENBERG	1996	Mortality	Some concerns	High	Some concerns	Low	Low	High risk	Low risk
		VTE	Some concerns	High	Some concerns	Low	Low	High risk	Low risk
		Major bleeding	Some concerns	High	Some concerns	Low	Low	High risk	Low risk
HILLBOM	2002	Mortality	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low risk	Unclear or high risk
		VTE	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low risk	Unclear or high risk
		Major bleeding	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low risk	Unclear or high risk
ISHI	2013	Major bleeding	High	Low	Low	Some concerns	Some concerns	High risk	Unclear or high risk
		Mortality	Low	Some concerns	Low	Low	Low	High risk	Low risk
IST	1997	VTE	Low	Some concerns	Low	Some concerns	Low	High risk	Low risk
		Major bleeding	Low	Some concerns	Low	Some concerns	Low	High risk	Low risk
		Mortality	Low	Some concerns	Low	Some concerns	Low	High risk	Low risk
KAKKAR	2011	Major bleeding	Low	Some concerns	Low	Some concerns	Low	High risk	Low risk
		Mortality	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low risk	Unclear or high risk
		VTE	Low	Low	Some concerns	Low	Low	High risk	Unclear or high risk
KAPOOR	1999	Major bleeding	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low risk	Unclear or high risk
		VTE	Some concerns	High	Some concerns	High	Some concerns	High risk	Unclear or high risk
		Mortality	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low risk	Unclear or high risk
KAY	1995	VTE	Low	Low	Low	Some concerns	Low	High risk	Unclear or high risk
		Mortality	Some concerns	High	Some concerns	High	Some concerns	High risk	Unclear or high risk
		VTE	Some concerns	High	Some concerns	High	Some concerns	High risk	Unclear or high risk
KLEBER	2003	Major bleeding	Some concerns	Some concerns	Low	Low	Low	High risk	Unclear or high risk
		Mortality	Some concerns	Some concerns	Some concerns	Low	Low	High risk	Unclear or high risk
		VTE	Some concerns	Some concerns	Some concerns	Low	Low	High risk	Unclear or high risk
LECHLER	1996	Major bleeding	Some concerns	Some concerns	Low	Low	Low	High risk	Unclear or high risk
		SAE	Some concerns	Some concerns	Low	Low	Low	High risk	Unclear or high risk
		Mortality	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low risk	Low risk
LEDERLE	2006	VTE	Low	Low	Some concerns	Low	Low	High risk	Low risk
		Major bleeding	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low risk	Low risk
		Mortality	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low risk	Low risk
LEIZOROVICZ	2004	VTE	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low risk	Low risk
		Major bleeding	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low risk	Low risk
		Mortality	Low	Low	Some concerns	Low	Low	High risk	Unclear or high risk
LEVI	2007	VTE	Low	Low	Some concerns	Low	Low	High risk	Unclear or high risk
		Major bleeding	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low risk	Unclear or high risk
		VTE	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low risk	Low risk
MAHE	2005	SAE	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low risk	Low risk
		Mortality	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low risk	Unclear or high risk
		VTE	Low	Low	High	Low	Low	High risk	Unclear or high risk
MCCARTHY	1977	Major bleeding	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low risk	Unclear or high risk
		Mortality	High	Some concerns	Low	Low	Some concerns	High risk	Low risk
		VTE	Some concerns	Some concerns	Low	Low	Some concerns	High risk	Unclear or high risk
NCT00445328	2009	Major bleeding	Some concerns	Some concerns	Some concerns	Some concerns	Some concerns	High risk	Unclear or high risk
		Mortality	Some concerns	Some concerns	Some concerns	Low	Some concerns	High risk	Unclear or high risk
		VTE	Some concerns	Some concerns	Some concerns	Some concerns	Some concerns	High risk	Unclear or high risk
PRANDONI	1986	Major bleeding	Some concerns	Some concerns	Some concerns	Some concerns	Some concerns	High risk	Unclear or high risk
		SAE	Some concerns	Some concerns	Some concerns	Some concerns	Some concerns	High risk	Unclear or high risk
		VTE	Low	High	Some concerns	Low	Some concerns	High risk	Unclear or high risk
PRINS	1989	Mortality	Some concerns	Low	Low	Low	Some concerns	High risk	Unclear or high risk

Table S7. Bias assessment of 44 RCTs included in main analysis

Author	Year	Outcome	Bias arising from randomisation process	Bias due to deviations from interventions	Bias from missing outcome data	Bias in measurement of the outcome	Bias in selection of the reported results	Overall bias judgement	Risk of vested interests
PONIEWIERSKI	1988	Major bleeding	Some concerns	Low	High	Low	Some concerns	High risk	Unclear or high risk
		VTE	Low	Some concerns	Low	Low	Some concerns	High risk	Low risk
RIESS	2010	Major bleeding	Low	Some concerns	Low	Low	Some concerns	High risk	Low risk
		Mortality	Low	Low	Some concerns	Low	Low	High risk	Unclear or high risk
		VTE	Low	Some concerns	Some concerns	Low	Low	High risk	Unclear or high risk
		Major bleeding	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low risk	Unclear or high risk
SAMAMA	1999	SAE	Low	Low	Some concerns	Low	Low	High risk	Unclear or high risk
		Mortality	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low risk	Unclear or high risk
		VTE	Low	High	Some concerns	Low	Low	High risk	Unclear or high risk
SANDSET	1990	Major bleeding	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low risk	Unclear or high risk
		Mortality	Some concerns	Low	Low	Low	Low	High risk	Unclear or high risk
		VTE	Some concerns	High	Low	Low	Low	High risk	Unclear or high risk
SCHELLONG	2010	Major bleeding	Some concerns	Low	Low	Low	Low	High risk	Unclear or high risk
		Mortality	Low	Some concerns	High	Low	Low	High risk	Unclear or high risk
		VTE	Low	Some concerns	High	Some concerns	Low	High risk	Unclear or high risk
		Major bleeding	Low	Some concerns	High	Some concerns	Low	High risk	Unclear or high risk
SHERMAN	2007	SAE	Low	Some concerns	High	Some concerns	Low	High risk	Unclear or high risk
		Mortality	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low risk	Unclear or high risk
		VTE	Low	Low	Some concerns	Low	Low	High risk	Unclear or high risk
WARLOW	1973	Major bleeding	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low risk	Unclear or high risk
		Mortality	Some concerns	Low	Low	Low	Some concerns	High risk	Low risk
		VTE	Some concerns	Low	Low	Low	Some concerns	High risk	Low risk
ZAWILSKA	1989	Major bleeding	Some concerns	Low	Low	Low	Some concerns	High risk	Low risk
		Mortality	High	Some concerns	Low	Low	Some concerns	High risk	Unclear or high risk
		VTE	High	Some concerns	Low	Some concerns	Some concerns	High risk	Unclear or high risk
		Major bleeding	High	Some concerns	Low	Some concerns	Some concerns	High risk	Unclear or high risk

SAE: serious adverse events; VTE: venous thromboembolism.

Table S8. Benefits and harms of all anticoagulants with placebo as reference

	Pairwise MA OR (95% CI)	NMA direct estimate OR (95% CrI)	NMA indirect estimate OR (95% CrI)	NMA total estimate OR (95% CrI)	TSA direct estimate OR (95% TSA-adj. CI)	Quality of evidence (basis for downgrades(s))
<u>Mortality</u>						
None	-	-	1.20 (0.96 to 1.58)	1.20 (0.96 to 1.58)	-	
LMWH (dose)						
Low	1.02 (0.83 to 1.26)	1.04 (0.81 to 1.36)	1.35 (0.94 to 2.16)	1.13 (0.93 to 1.40) ^b	1.02 (0.43 to 2.41)	Moderate (imprecision)
Intermediate	0.97 (0.86 to 1.10)	0.97 (0.81 to 1.18)	0.79 (0.49 to 1.23)	0.95 (0.81 to 1.10)	0.97 (0.80 to 1.18) ^b	Low (indirectness, imprecision)
UFH (dose)						
Low	1.24 (0.36 to 4.3) ^a	1.26 (0.34 to 4.66) ^a	1.09 (0.89 to 1.38)	1.09 (0.89 to 1.38)	Insufficient data	Low (within-study bias, imprecision)
Intermediate	-	-	1.13 (0.90 to 1.41)	1.13 (0.90 to 1.41)	-	Low (within-study bias, imprecision)
Pentasaccharides	0.53 (0.27 to 1.03) ^a	0.52 (0.25 to 1.04) ^a	-	0.52 (0.25 to 1.04) ^a	Insufficient data	Moderate (imprecision)
DOACs	-	-	1.09 (0.71 to 1.64) ^a	1.09 (0.71 to 1.64) ^a	-	Low (within-study bias, imprecision)
<u>Venous thromboembolism</u>						
None	-	-	1.53 (0.93 to 2.59)	1.53 (0.93 to 2.59)	-	
LMWH (dose)						
Low	0.78 (0.51 to 1.21)	0.76 (0.44 to 1.30)	0.96 (0.40 to 2.38)	0.82 (0.53 to 1.29)	Insufficient data	Very low (within-study bias, imprecision)
Intermediate	0.76 (0.54 to 1.08)	0.75 (0.49 to 1.13)	0.34 (0.10 to 0.90)	0.66 (0.46 to 0.93)	0.76 (0.19 to 3.14)	Low (within-study bias, indirectness)
UFH (dose)						
Low	0.75 (0.25 to 2.32)	0.87 (0.43 to 1.60)	1.23 (0.66 to 2.31)	1.05 (0.68 to 1.56)	Insufficient data	Very low (within-study bias, indirectness, imprecision)
Intermediate	-	-	0.71 (0.43 to 1.19)	0.71 (0.43 to 1.19)	-	Low (within-study bias, imprecision)
Pentasaccharides	0.35 (0.11 to 1.11) ^a	0.32 (0.08 to 1.07) ^a	-	0.32 (0.08 to 1.07) ^a	Insufficient data	Low (imprecision, heterogeneity)
DOACs	-	-	0.68 (0.33 to 1.34)	0.68 (0.33 to 1.34)	-	Very low (within-study bias, imprecision)
<u>Major bleeding</u>						
None	-	-	0.68 (0.23 to 2.07)	0.68 (0.23 to 2.07)	-	
LMWH (dose)						
Low	0.86 (0.31 to 2.41)	0.85 (0.30 to 2.35)	1.53 (0.38 to 5.05)	1.05 (0.45 to 2.26)	Insufficient data	Low (within-study bias, imprecision)
Intermediate	1.49 (0.83 to 2.70)	1.48 (0.72 to 2.99)	1.05 (0.22 to 5.41)	1.37 (0.70 to 2.67)	Insufficient data	Moderate (imprecision)
UFH (dose)						
Low	-	-	1.51 (0.68 to 3.86)	1.51 (0.68 to 3.86)	-	Low (imprecision)
Intermediate	-	-	2.63 (1.00 to 6.21)	2.63 (1.00 to 6.21)	-	Low (within-study bias, heterogeneity)
Pentasaccharides	0.97 (0.06 to 15.6) ^a	0.96 (0.02 to 46.3) ^a	-	0.96 (0.02 to 46.3) ^a	Insufficient data	Low (imprecision)
DOACs	-	-	2.31 (0.82 to 6.47)	2.31 (0.82 to 6.47)	-	Low (within-study bias, heterogeneity)

Table S8. Benefits and harms of all anticoagulants with placebo as reference

	<u>Serious adverse events</u>					
None	-	-	-	-	-	
LMWH (dose)						
Low	1.38 (0.73 to 2.61) ^a	1.38 (0.41 to 4.64) ^a	2.05 (0.33 to 8.67)	1.62 (0.63 to 3.67)	Insufficient data	Very low (within-study bias, heterogeneity)
Intermediate	1.11 (0.92 to 1.34) ^a	1.11 (0.37 to 3.30) ^a	0.76 (0.16 to 5.02)	1.05 (0.46 to 2.35)	Insufficient data	Low (indirectness, imprecision)
UFH (dose)						
Low	-	-	1.19 (0.29 to 5.15)	1.19 (0.29 to 5.15)	-	Low (imprecision)
Intermediate	-	-	2.19 (0.87 to 5.82)	2.19 (0.87 to 5.82)	-	Very low (within-study bias, heterogeneity)

Safety and efficacy of tested interventions with placebo as reference. Small differences in direct estimates between pairwise and network meta-analysis may be caused by differences in zero-event handling. CI: confidence interval; CrI: credible interval; DOAC: direct oral anticoagulant; LMWH: low-molecular-weight heparin; MA: meta-analysis; NMA: network meta-analysis; OR: odds ratio; TSA: trial sequential analysis; UFH: unfractionated heparin. ^a Estimate is based on one RCT; ^b the TSA boundary for futility was crossed which suggests that future RCTs will not change conclusions.

Table S9. Sensitivity analyses with placebo as reference

	Main	Sensitivity 1	Sensitivity 2	Sensitivity 3	Sensitivity 4.1	Sensitivity 4.2
	<u>Mortality</u>					
None	1.20 (0.96 to 1.58)	1.17 (0.94 to 1.47)	1.19 (0.96 to 1.56)	1.04 (0.58 to 2.25)	1.20 (0.95 to 1.59)	1.20 (0.96 to 1.56)
LMWH (dose)						
Low	1.13 (0.93 to 1.40)	1.11 (0.92 to 1.36)	1.00 (0.88 to 1.15)	1.22 (0.86 to 2.10)	1.13 (0.94 to 1.41)	1.13 (0.93 to 1.39)
Intermediate	0.95 (0.81 to 1.10)	0.96 (0.82 to 1.10)		0.86 (0.52 to 1.54)	0.95 (0.81 to 1.11)	0.95 (0.81 to 1.1)
UFH (dose)						
Low	1.09 (0.89 to 1.38)	1.08 (0.89 to 1.31)	1.11 (0.92 to 1.34)	0.98 (0.60 to 1.83)	1.09 (0.89 to 1.38)	1.09 (0.90 to 1.36)
Intermediate	1.13 (0.90 to 1.41)	1.12 (0.90 to 1.37)		1.00 (0.58 to 1.89)	1.13 (0.90 to 1.42)	1.13 (0.90 to 1.41)
Pentasaccharides	0.52 (0.25 to 1.04)	0.53 (0.26 to 1.05)	0.52 (0.26 to 1.04)	-	0.52 (0.26 to 1.02)	0.53 (0.25 to 1.04)
DOACs	1.09 (0.71 to 1.64)	1.09 (0.72 to 1.64)	1.14 (0.76 to 1.72)	0.98 (0.46 to 2.46)	1.08 (0.72 to 1.65)	1.08 (0.72 to 1.64)
	<u>Venous thromboembolism</u>					
None	1.53 (0.93 to 2.59)	1.63 (0.98 to 3.14)	1.52 (0.9 to 2.62)	1.64 (0.53 to 6.8)	1.52 (0.93 to 2.60)	1.52 (0.94 to 2.48)
LMWH (dose)						
Low	0.82 (0.53 to 1.29)	0.73 (0.43 to 1.20)	0.74 (0.54 to 1.00)	0.70 (0.23 to 1.59)	0.82 (0.53 to 1.28)	0.82 (0.54 to 1.26)
Intermediate	0.66 (0.46 to 0.93)	0.55 (0.36 to 0.79)		0.52 (0.15 to 1.06)	0.66 (0.46 to 0.94)	0.66 (0.46 to 0.93)
UFH (dose)						
Low	1.05 (0.68 to 1.56)	0.91 (0.56 to 1.37)	0.95 (0.63 to 1.41)	0.85 (0.26 to 1.68)	1.05 (0.69 to 1.57)	1.05 (0.71 to 1.56)
Intermediate	0.71 (0.43 to 1.19)	0.67 (0.40 to 1.19)		0.68 (0.21 to 1.79)	0.70 (0.43 to 1.19)	0.70 (0.43 to 1.17)
Pentasaccharides	0.32 (0.08 to 1.07)	0.33 (0.08 to 1.18)	0.33 (0.08 to 1.05)	-	0.33 (0.08 to 1.06)	0.33 (0.09 to 1.04)
DOACs	0.68 (0.33 to 1.34)	0.54 (0.23 to 1.15)	0.75 (0.37 to 1.44)	0.50 (0.09 to 1.41)	0.67 (0.33 to 1.31)	0.67 (0.34 to 1.31)
	<u>Major bleeding</u>					
None	0.68 (0.23 to 2.07)	0.81 (0.28 to 3.13)	0.57 (0.24 to 1.77)	0.82 (0.25 to 2.82)	0.68 (0.23 to 2.08)	0.67 (0.29 to 1.54)
LMWH (dose)						
Low	1.05 (0.45 to 2.26)	1.03 (0.42 to 2.30)	1.30 (0.72 to 2.27)	1.79 (0.67 to 4.40)	1.07 (0.46 to 2.24)	1.11 (0.55 to 2.15)
Intermediate	1.37 (0.70 to 2.67)	1.55 (0.78 to 3.24)		1.56 (0.72 to 3.52)	1.38 (0.70 to 2.66)	1.37 (0.79 to 2.42)
UFH (dose)						
Low	1.51 (0.68 to 3.86)	1.58 (0.70 to 4.52)	1.76 (0.92 to 3.90)	1.54 (0.64 to 4.28)	1.47 (0.69 to 3.86)	1.38 (0.72 to 2.88)
Intermediate	2.63 (1.00 to 6.21)	2.44 (0.89 to 5.92)		3.60 (1.28 to 9.04)	2.71 (1.01 to 6.13)	2.89 (1.28 to 5.78)
Pentasaccharides	0.96 (0.02 to 46.3)	0.98 (0.02 to 44.8)	0.98 (0.03 to 38.4)	0.95 (0.02 to 37.9)	0.98 (0.02 to 42.2)	1.00 (0.02 to 44.1)
DOACs	2.31 (0.82 to 6.47)	2.80 (0.94 to 9.29)	2.21 (0.88 to 5.32)	2.67 (0.91 to 7.95)	2.34 (0.82 to 6.46)	2.35 (1.01 to 5.48)

Table S9. Sensitivity analyses with placebo as reference

	Main	Sensitivity 1	Sensitivity 2	Sensitivity 3	Sensitivity 4.1	Sensitivity 4.2
	<u>Serious adverse events</u>					
LMWH (dose)						
Low	1.62 (0.63 to 3.67)	1.63 (0.62 to 3.65)	1.17 (0.60 to 2.44)	-	1.61 (0.46 to 4.49)	1.67 (0.84 to 3.09)
Intermediate	1.05 (0.46 to 2.35)	1.06 (0.46 to 2.34)		-	1.06 (0.36 to 3.15)	1.06 (0.63 to 1.71)
UFH (dose)						
Low	1.19 (0.29 to 5.15)	1.17 (0.29 to 4.99)	1.63 (0.78 to 4.43)	-	1.19 (0.24 to 7.00)	1.16 (0.35 to 3.85)
Intermediate	2.19 (0.87 to 5.82)	2.18 (0.88 to 5.79)		-	2.17 (0.68 to 7.62)	2.14 (1.12 to 4.32)

Sensitivity analyses with placebo as reference. Data are odds ratio (OR) with 95% credible interval. Main: main analysis. Sensitivity 1: network meta-analysis including all eligible studies and interventions irrespective of transitivity considerations. Sensitivity 2: network meta-analysis including interventions on a grouped level irrespective of dose. Sensitivity 3: network meta-analysis including all studies with a follow-up duration limited to 30 days. Sensitivity 4.1: network meta-analysis assuming a uniform prior distribution for the between-trial standard deviation: $U(0,5)$. Sensitivity 4.2: network meta-analysis assuming empirical prior distributions based on Turner et al. [4], for mortality: log-normal $(-4.27, 1.48^2)$; for all other outcomes log-normal $(-3.23, 1.88^2)$. DOACs: direct oral anticoagulants; LMWH: low-molecular-weight heparin; UFH: unfractionated heparin.

Table S10. Subgroup analyses with placebo as reference

	Main	Subgroup 1	Subgroup 2	Subgroup 3	Subgroup 4.1	Subgroup 4.2	Subgroup 4.3
	<u>Mortality</u>						
None	1.20 (0.96 to 1.58)	-	1.25 (0.52 to 3.45)	-	1.21 (0.79 to 1.99)	1.19 (0.91 to 1.72)	1.49 (0.69 to 3.53)
LMWH (dose)							
Low	1.13 (0.93 to 1.40)	1.09 (0.84 to 1.45)	3.22 (0.89 to 12.9)	1.09 (0.81 to 1.63)	1.08 (0.85 to 1.42)	1.13 (0.92 to 1.47)	1.80 (0.93 to 3.61)
Intermediate	0.95 (0.81 to 1.10)	0.90 (0.67 to 1.10)	0.97 (0.48 to 1.96)	0.95 (0.71 to 1.17)	0.94 (0.75 to 1.12)	0.95 (0.80 to 1.13)	1.11 (0.56 to 2.22)
UFH (dose)							
Low	1.09 (0.89 to 1.38)	1.01 (0.69 to 1.37)	1.15 (0.53 to 2.57)	1.07 (0.74 to 1.53)	1.12 (0.84 to 1.60)	1.09 (0.84 to 1.48)	1.29 (0.64 to 2.70)
Intermediate	1.13 (0.90 to 1.41)	1.06 (0.62 to 1.79)	1.25 (0.53 to 3.19)	1.25 (0.86 to 1.92)	1.12 (0.78 to 1.62)	1.13 (0.87 to 1.48)	1.30 (0.61 to 2.80)
Pentasaccharides	0.52 (0.25 to 1.04)	0.52 (0.25 to 1.08)	-	0.52 (0.24 to 1.09)	0.52 (0.25 to 1.08)	0.53 (0.25 to 1.05)	-
DOACs	1.09 (0.71 to 1.64)	-	-	1.08 (0.61 to 1.79)	1.07 (0.64 to 1.73)	1.09 (0.70 to 1.69)	-
	<u>Venous thromboembolism</u>						
None	1.53 (0.93 to 2.59)	-	1.34 (0.31 to 5.55)	-	1.40 (0.71 to 2.96)	1.65 (0.77 to 3.55)	1.45 (0.38 to 5.41)
LMWH (dose)							
Low	0.82 (0.53 to 1.29)	4.06 (0.30 to 53.7)	0.72 (0.09 to 5.96)	0.87 (0.46 to 1.86)	0.87 (0.53 to 1.46)	0.85 (0.53 to 1.36)	0.66 (0.10 to 3.95)
Intermediate	0.66 (0.46 to 0.93)	0.71 (0.32 to 1.44)	0.60 (0.22 to 1.20)	0.74 (0.47 to 1.16)	0.71 (0.48 to 1.03)	0.63 (0.39 to 0.99)	0.61 (0.19 to 1.27)
UFH (dose)							
Low	1.05 (0.68 to 1.56)	1.03 (0.43 to 2.31)	0.93 (0.32 to 1.98)	1.11 (0.63 to 2.01)	0.98 (0.59 to 1.58)	1.19 (0.58 to 2.37)	0.97 (0.30 to 1.98)
Intermediate	0.71 (0.43 to 1.19)	1.70 (0.26 to 10.5)	0.69 (0.20 to 2.81)	0.83 (0.35 to 2.11)	0.82 (0.39 to 1.79)	0.76 (0.41 to 1.43)	0.63 (0.17 to 2.02)
Pentasaccharides	0.32 (0.08 to 1.07)	0.35 (0.09 to 1.42)	-	0.32 (0.08 to 1.16)	0.35 (0.10 to 1.20)	0.35 (0.10 to 1.18)	-
DOACs	0.68 (0.33 to 1.34)	0.45 (0.13 to 1.54)	-	0.74 (0.32 to 1.61)	0.73 (0.34 to 1.49)	0.65 (0.29 to 1.36)	-
	<u>Major bleeding</u>						
None	0.68 (0.23 to 2.07)	-	0.23 (0.01 to 4.65)	-	0.95 (0.17 to 7.94)	0.44 (0.13 to 1.67)	0.66 (0.02 to 24.3)
LMWH (dose)							
Low	1.05 (0.45 to 2.26)	0.81 (0.30 to 2.04)	1.37 (0.04 to 47.7)	0.57 (0.05 to 5.79)	0.85 (0.33 to 2.05)	0.75 (0.27 to 1.84)	2.28 (0.22 to 27.5)
Intermediate	1.37 (0.70 to 2.67)	1.29 (0.62 to 2.50)	0.35 (0.03 to 3.29)	0.90 (0.20 to 2.55)	1.50 (0.70 to 3.09)	1.31 (0.62 to 2.59)	1.11 (0.05 to 28.5)
UFH (dose)							
Low	1.51 (0.68 to 3.86)	1.17 (0.37 to 2.94)	0.37 (0.02 to 5.49)	1.02 (0.20 to 4.47)	2.37 (0.97 to 9.15)	0.92 (0.34 to 3.31)	1.21 (0.06 to 37.6)
Intermediate	2.63 (1.00 to 6.21)	1.61 (0.47 to 5.10)	1.12 (0.06 to 18.6)	1.17 (0.09 to 16.0)	1.84 (0.61 to 5.95)	1.86 (0.65 to 4.94)	2.98 (0.12 to 61.1)
Pentasaccharides	0.96 (0.02 to 46.3)	1.01 (0.02 to 41.3)	-	1.00 (0.02 to 47.1)	0.96 (0.02 to 44.8)	1.00 (0.02 to 44.4)	-
DOACs	2.31 (0.82 to 6.47)	1.77 (0.51 to 5.91)	-	1.52 (0.23 to 5.92)	2.54 (0.78 to 7.77)	2.23 (0.72 to 6.23)	-

Table S10. Subgroup analyses with placebo as reference

	Main	Subgroup 1	Subgroup 2	Subgroup 3	Subgroup 4.1	Subgroup 4.2	Subgroup 4.3
	<u>Serious adverse events</u>						
LMWH (dose)							
Low	1.62 (0.63 to 3.67)	0.46 (0.02 to 8.27)	-	-	-	-	-
Intermediate	1.05 (0.46 to 2.35)	1.11 (0.59 to 2.07)	-	-	-	-	-
UFH (dose)							
Low	1.19 (0.29 to 5.15)	0.92 (0.23 to 3.62)	-	-	-	-	-
Intermediate	2.19 (0.87 to 5.82)	-	-	-	-	-	-

Subgroup analyses with placebo as reference. Data are odds ratio (OR) with 95% credible interval. Main: main analysis. Subgroup 1: network meta-analysis of low risk of bias RCTs. Subgroup 2: network meta-analysis of low risk of vested interest RCTs. Subgroup 3: network meta-analysis of trials published on or after the median publication year (exact year differs per outcome). Subgroup 4.1: network meta-analysis excluding RCTs in stroke patients. Subgroup 4.2: network meta-analysis excluding RCTs in critically ill patients. Subgroup 4.3: network meta-analysis excluding RCTs in medically ill patients. DOACs: direct oral anticoagulants; LMWH: low-molecular-weight heparin; UFH: unfractionated heparin.

Table S11. Sensitivity analysis with placebo and ‘no treatment’ grouped into a single control arm

	Main analysis with placebo as reference treatment	Sensitivity analysis 5 with ‘control’ as reference treatment
<u>Mortality</u>		
LMWH (dose)		
Low	1.13 (0.93 to 1.40)	1.06 (0.89 to 1.28)
Intermediate	0.95 (0.81 to 1.10)	0.89 (0.78 to 1.01)
UFH (dose)		
Low	1.09 (0.89 to 1.38)	0.96 (0.85 to 1.10)
Intermediate	1.13 (0.90 to 1.41)	0.99 (0.85 to 1.15)
Pentasaccharides	0.52 (0.25 to 1.04)	0.52 (0.25 to 1.02)
DOACs	1.09 (0.71 to 1.64)	1.02 (0.67 to 1.53)
<u>Venous thromboembolism</u>		
LMWH (dose)		
Low	0.82 (0.53 to 1.29)	0.74 (0.49 to 1.14)
Intermediate	0.66 (0.46 to 0.93)	0.58 (0.41 to 0.81)
UFH (dose)		
Low	1.05 (0.68 to 1.56)	0.81 (0.60 to 1.06)
Intermediate	0.71 (0.43 to 1.19)	0.55 (0.36 to 0.86)
Pentasaccharides	0.32 (0.08 to 1.07)	0.33 (0.09 to 1.06)
DOACs	0.68 (0.33 to 1.34)	0.60 (0.29 to 1.15)
<u>Major bleeding</u>		
LMWH (dose)		
Low	1.05 (0.45 to 2.26)	1.27 (0.58 to 2.36)
Intermediate	1.37 (0.70 to 2.67)	1.62 (0.88 to 2.70)
UFH (dose)		
Low	1.51 (0.68 to 3.86)	1.84 (1.09 to 3.62)
Intermediate	2.63 (1.00 to 6.21)	3.56 (1.45 to 6.10)
Pentasaccharides	0.96 (0.02 to 46.3)	0.96 (0.02 to 39.2)
DOACs	2.31 (0.82 to 6.47)	2.75 (1.00 to 6.84)
<u>Serious adverse events</u>		
LMWH (dose)		
Low	1.62 (0.63 to 3.67)	-
Intermediate	1.05 (0.46 to 2.35)	-
UFH (dose)		
Low	1.19 (0.29 to 5.15)	-
Intermediate	2.19 (0.87 to 5.82)	-

Sensitivity analysis 5: network meta-analysis with ‘placebo and no treatment’ as a single node in the network. For comparisons the results from the main analyses with placebo as a reference treatment, are displayed in the left column. The results from sensitivity analysis 5, compared to a control group in which both placebo and ‘no treatment’ were merged, are displayed in the right column. DOACs: direct oral anticoagulants; LMWH: low-molecular-weight heparin; UFH: unfractionated heparin.

Table S12. Prediction intervals

	95% Credible interval	95% Prediction interval
<u>Mortality</u>		
LMWH (dose)		
Low	1.13 (0.93 to 1.40)	1.13 (0.87 to 1.55)
Intermediate	0.95 (0.81 to 1.10)	0.95 (0.73 to 1.23)
UFH (dose)		
Low	1.09 (0.89 to 1.38)	1.09 (0.83 to 1.50)
Intermediate	1.13 (0.90 to 1.41)	1.14 (0.84 to 1.54)
Pentasaccharides	0.52 (0.25 to 1.04)	0.53 (0.25 to 1.08)
DOACs	1.09 (0.71 to 1.64)	1.08 (0.68 to 1.71)
<u>Venous Thromboembolism</u>		
LMWH (dose)		
Low	0.82 (0.53 to 1.29)	0.82 (0.47 to 1.48)
Intermediate	0.66 (0.46 to 0.93)	0.66 (0.38 to 1.08)
UFH (dose)		
Low	1.05 (0.68 to 1.56)	1.05 (0.59 to 1.81)
Intermediate	0.71 (0.43 to 1.19)	0.70 (0.38 to 1.37)
Pentasaccharides	0.32 (0.08 to 1.07)	0.33 (0.08 to 1.12)
DOACs	0.68 (0.33 to 1.34)	0.68 (0.30 to 1.43)
<u>Major bleeding</u>		
LMWH (dose)		
Low	1.05 (0.45 to 2.26)	1.09 (0.27 to 3.65)
Intermediate	1.37 (0.70 to 2.67)	1.38 (0.39 to 4.72)
UFH (dose)		
Low	1.51 (0.68 to 3.86)	1.45 (0.43 to 6.54)
Intermediate	2.63 (1.00 to 6.21)	2.75 (0.62 to 9.55)
Pentasaccharides	0.96 (0.02 to 46.3)	0.92 (0.02 to 43.4)
DOACs	2.31 (0.82 to 6.47)	2.34 (0.52 to 9.90)
<u>Serious adverse events</u>		
LMWH (dose)		
Low	1.62 (0.63 to 3.67)	1.64 (0.41 to 5.48)
Intermediate	1.05 (0.46 to 2.35)	1.06 (0.30 to 3.71)
UFH (dose)		
Low	1.19 (0.29 to 5.15)	1.17 (0.23 to 6.76)
Intermediate	2.19 (0.87 to 5.82)	2.17 (0.60 to 8.49)

Main analyses with 95% credible intervals and 95% prediction intervals. Data are odds ratio (OR) with respective 95% credible (left column) or prediction intervals (right column). Prediction intervals may reflect the variation in treatment effects over different settings, including what effect is to be expected in future patients. DOACs: direct oral anticoagulants; LMWH: low-molecular-weight heparin; UFH: unfractionated heparin

Table S13. Mean ranks

	<u>Mortality</u>	<u>Venous Thromboembolism</u>	<u>Major bleeding</u>	<u>Serious adverse events</u>
	<i>Mean rank</i>	<i>Mean rank</i>	<i>Mean rank</i>	<i>Mean rank</i>
No intervention	7.0	7.9	1.9	-
Placebo	3.6	6	3.1	2.0
LMWH (dose)				
Low	5.8	4.5	3.4	3.5
Intermediate	2.5	2.9	4.7	2.2
UFH (dose)				
Low	5.1	6.2	5.1	2.7
Intermediate	5.8	3.4	7.2	4.6
Pentasaccharides	1.2	1.6	3.9	-
DOACs	5.0	3.4	6.7	-

Mean ranks for each intervention and each outcome, based on the main analyses. The mean rank is the mean of the distribution of the ranking probabilities. This indicates the probability that an intervention is 'best', 'second-best', et cetera. For example, pentasaccharides and intermediate dose LMWH ranked best for preventing venous thromboembolism, whereas 'no intervention' ranked worst.

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R code for main and node-splitting models

Network meta-analysis of mortality

```
#load helper functions
source(here("Functions", "functions.R"), local = knitr::knit_global())

#load data files
load(here("Data", "data.RData"))

# Define network
#sensitivity set
sensitivity <- m

#vector of studies focusing on populations of primary interest
pop <- data %>%
  filter(population %in% c("cardiology", "critically ill", "medical", "stroke")) %>%
  pull(study) %>%
  unique()

#vector of studies with uncommonly used interventions that may add heterogeneity
int.sparse <- data %>%
  filter(treatment %in% c("vka", "tar", "heparinoid")) %>%
  pull(study) %>%
  unique()

#main data, excluding uncommonly used interventions
m <- m %>%
  filter(study %in% pop & !study %in% int.sparse)

#basic descriptives
dscr <- data.prep(arm.data = m,
  varname.t = "treatment",
  varname.s = "study")

char <- net.tab(data = dscr,
  outcome = "responders",
  N = "sampleSize",
  type.outcome = "binomial",
  time = NULL)

#network summary statistics
char$network
#network summary statistics by treatment
char$intervention
#network summary statistics according to direct comparisons
char$comparison

#network of all eligible trials, numbers represent direct comparisons
network <- mtc.network(data = m, treatments = treat.code[treat.code$id %in% m$treatment,])
net.plot(dscr, node.scale = 2, edge.scale=2,study.counts=TRUE)

# Define and run the model
#define NMA model
model <- mtc.model(network,
  linearModel = "random",
  type = "consistency",
  likelihood = "binom",
```

R code for main and node-splitting models

```
link = "logit",  
n.chain = 4,  
hy.prior = mtc.hy.prior("std.dev", "dunif", 0, "om.scale")) #set vague prior for between study heterogeneity
```

#run model

```
m.mcmc <- mtc.run(model,  
  n.adapt = 50000, #burn-in  
  n.iter = 250000, #iterations  
  thin = 10)
```

Algorithm convergence

#algorithm convergence, iteration plots

```
plot(m.mcmc)  
gelman.plot(m.mcmc)
```

#overall PSFR

```
diag <- gelman.diag(m.mcmc); diag$psrf; diag$mpsrf
```

Model fit

```
m.mcmc$deviance$Dbar #residual deviance  
m.mcmc$deviance$`data points` #total data points  
m.mcmc$deviance$pD #effective parameters  
m.mcmc$deviance$DIC #deviance information criterion
```

```
deviance <- mtc.deviance(m.mcmc)
```

#residual deviance plot

```
mtc.devplot.annotated(deviance)
```

#leverage plot

```
mtc.levplot.annotated(deviance)
```

Consistency: nodesplitting

#assessment of consistency

```
m.nodesplit <- mtc.nodesplit(network,  
  linearModel = "random",  
  n.adapt = 50000,  
  n.iter = 250000,  
  thin = 10)
```

Consistency: nodesplitting results

```
mtc.nodesplit.comparisons(network)
```

```
plot(summary(m.nodesplit))
```

Inferences

#overall results

```
summary(m.mcmc)
```

#efficacy compared to no intervention

```
forest(relative.effect(m.mcmc, t1 = "none"), use.description = TRUE)
```

#efficacy compared to placebo

```
forest(relative.effect(m.mcmc, t1 = "placebo"), use.description = TRUE)
```

R code for main and node-splitting models

```
#rank probability
rank.prob <- rank.probability(m.mcmc, preferredDirection = -1)

#rankogram
plot(rank.prob, beside=TRUE, cex.names=0.75)

#SUCRA
cumrank.prob <- apply(t(rank.prob), 2, cumsum)
sucra <- round(colMeans(cumrank.prob[-nrow(cumrank.prob),]),4)
print(sucra)
```

Calculate mean ranks

```
#calculate mean ranks
ranks <- rank.prob
print(ranks)

meanranks <- as.table(c(
#DOAC
meanrank.doac <- 1*ranks[1,1] + 2*ranks[1,2] + 3*ranks[1,3] + 4*ranks[1,4]+ 5*ranks[1,5] + 6*ranks[1,6] + 7*ranks[1,7] + 8*ranks[1,8],
#lmwh_int
meanrank.lmwh_int <- 1*ranks[2,1] + 2*ranks[2,2] + 3*ranks[2,3] + 4*ranks[2,4]+ 5*ranks[2,5] + 6*ranks[2,6] + 7*ranks[2,7] + 8*ranks[2,8],
#lmwh_low
meanrank.lmwh_low <- 1*ranks[3,1] + 2*ranks[3,2] + 3*ranks[3,3] + 4*ranks[3,4]+ 5*ranks[3,5] + 6*ranks[3,6] + 7*ranks[3,7] + 8*ranks[3,8],
#none
meanrank.none <- 1*ranks[4,1] + 2*ranks[4,2] + 3*ranks[4,3] + 4*ranks[4,4]+ 5*ranks[4,5] + 6*ranks[4,6] + 7*ranks[4,7] + 8*ranks[4,8],
#pentasach
meanrank.pentasach <- 1*ranks[5,1] + 2*ranks[5,2] + 3*ranks[5,3] + 4*ranks[5,4]+ 5*ranks[5,5] + 6*ranks[5,6] + 7*ranks[5,7] + 8*ranks[5,8],
#placebo
meanrank.placebo <- 1*ranks[6,1] + 2*ranks[6,2] + 3*ranks[6,3] + 4*ranks[6,4]+ 5*ranks[6,5] + 6*ranks[6,6] + 7*ranks[6,7] + 8*ranks[6,8],
#ufh_int
meanrank.ufh_int <- 1*ranks[7,1] + 2*ranks[7,2] + 3*ranks[7,3] + 4*ranks[7,4]+ 5*ranks[7,5] + 6*ranks[7,6] + 7*ranks[7,7] + 8*ranks[7,8],
#ufh_low
meanrank.ufh_low <- 1*ranks[8,1] + 2*ranks[8,2] + 3*ranks[8,3] + 4*ranks[8,4]+ 5*ranks[8,5] + 6*ranks[8,6] + 7*ranks[8,7] + 8*ranks[8,8]
))

print(round(meanranks,1))
```

Overview of prior distributions

```
#between-trial standard deviation:
m.mcmc$model$hy.prior
m.mcmc$model$om.scale

#trial baselines and effect estimates:
#obtain standard deviation for the relative effects prior (normal distribution).
m.mcmc$model$re.prior.sd

#calculate the precision:
1/(m.mcmc$model$re.prior.sd^2)
```

R code for main and node-splitting models

```
# Calculate prediction intervals
#rename treatments to numeric
tmp <- m %>% mutate(treatment = ifelse(treatment=="placebo",1,
  ifelse(treatment=="none",2,
  ifelse(treatment=="lmwh_low",3,
  ifelse(treatment=="lmwh_int",4,
  ifelse(treatment=="ufh_low",5,
  ifelse(treatment=="ufh_int",6,
  ifelse(treatment=="pentasach",7,
  ifelse(treatment=="doac",8,NA))))))))))

#redefine the network in order to retrieve the data in the format required for the gemtc rjags code
network <- mtc.network(data = tmp)

model <- mtc.model(network,
  linearModel = "random",
  type = "consistency",
  likelihood = "binom",
  link = "logit",
  n.chain = 4,
  hy.prior = mtc.hy.prior("std.dev", "dunif", 0, "om.scale"))

dat <- model$dat

#define the rjags code, based on gemtc output and supplemented to calculate prediction intervals
model <- "model {
  # Likelihood for arm-based data
  for (i in studies.a) {
    for (k in 1:na[i]) {
      logit(p[i, k]) <- mu[i] + delta[i, k]
      r[i, k] ~ dbin(p[i, k], n[i, k])

      rhat[i, k] <- p[i, k] * n[i, k]
      dev[i, k] <- 2 *
        (r[i, k] * (log(r[i, k]) - log(rhat[i, k])) +
          (n[i, k]-r[i, k]) * (log(n[i, k] - r[i, k]) - log(n[i, k] - rhat[i, k])))
    }
  }
  # Likelihood for contrast-based data (univariate for 2-arm trials)
  ## OMITTED
  # Likelihood for contrast-based data (multivariate for multi-arm trials)
  ## OMITTED

  # Random effects model
  for (i in studies) {
    # Study-level relative effects
    w[i, 1] <- 0
    delta[i, 1] <- 0
    for (k in 2:na[i]) { # parameterize multi-arm trials using a trick to avoid dnorm
      delta[i, k] ~ dnorm(md[i, k], taud[i, k])
      md[i, k] <- d[t[i, 1], t[i, k]] + sw[i, k]
      taud[i, k] <- tau.d * 2 * (k - 1) / k
      w[i, k] <- delta[i, k] - (d[t[i, 1], t[i, k]])
      sw[i, k] <- sum(w[i, 1:(k-1)]) / (k - 1)
    }
  }
}
```

R code for main and node-splitting models

```
# Random effects variance prior
sd.d ~ dunif(0, om.scale)
tau.d <- pow(sd.d, -2)

# Relative effect matrix
d[1, 1] <- 0
d[1, 2] <- d.1.5 + d.5.2
d[1, 3] <- d.1.3
d[1, 4] <- d.1.4
d[1, 5] <- d.1.5
d[1, 6] <- d.1.3 + d.3.6
d[1, 7] <- d.1.7
d[1, 8] <- d.1.4 + d.4.8
for (i in 2:nt) {
  for (j in 1:nt) {
    d[i, j] <- d[1, j] - d[1, i]
  }
}

prior.prec <- pow(re.prior.sd, -2)

# Study baseline priors
for (i in studies.a) {
  mu[i] ~ dnorm(0, prior.prec)
}

# Effect parameter priors
d.1.3 ~ dnorm(0, prior.prec)
d.1.4 ~ dnorm(0, prior.prec)
d.1.5 ~ dnorm(0, prior.prec)
d.1.7 ~ dnorm(0, prior.prec)
d.3.6 ~ dnorm(0, prior.prec)
d.4.8 ~ dnorm(0, prior.prec)
d.5.2 ~ dnorm(0, prior.prec)

# Prediction intervals
pred.d.12 ~ dnorm(d[1, 2], tau.d)
pred.d.13 ~ dnorm(d[1, 3], tau.d)
pred.d.14 ~ dnorm(d[1, 4], tau.d)
pred.d.15 ~ dnorm(d[1, 5], tau.d)
pred.d.16 ~ dnorm(d[1, 6], tau.d)
pred.d.17 ~ dnorm(d[1, 7], tau.d)
pred.d.18 ~ dnorm(d[1, 8], tau.d)

# Prediction intervals (odds ratio scale)
pred.or.12 <- exp(pred.d.12)
pred.or.13 <- exp(pred.d.13)
pred.or.14 <- exp(pred.d.14)
pred.or.15 <- exp(pred.d.15)
pred.or.16 <- exp(pred.d.16)
pred.or.17 <- exp(pred.d.17)
pred.or.18 <- exp(pred.d.18)
}"

#fit and run model
model.fit <- jags.model(file=textConnection(model), data = dat, n.chains = 4)

update(model.fit, 50000)
```

R code for main and node-splitting models

```
samples <- coda.samples(model.fit, n.iter=250000, thin = 10, variable.names = c("sd.d","pred.or.12","pred.or.13","pred.or.14","p
red.or.15","pred.or.16","pred.or.17","pred.or.18"))
#convergence
plot(samples, trace=TRUE, density = TRUE)

#prediction interval credible intervals
pred <- as.data.frame(summary(samples)[2]) %>%
  rownames_to_column() %>%
  select(rowname, quantiles.2.5., quantiles.50., quantiles.97.5.) %>%
  rename(comp = rowname, ci.l = quantiles.2.5., median=quantiles.50., ci.u=quantiles.97.5.) %>%
  mutate_if(is.numeric, round,2)

print(pred)
```

Network meta-analysis of venous thromboembolism

```
#load helper functions
source(here("Functions", "functions.R"), local = knitr::knit_global())
```

```
#load data files
load(here("Data", "data.RData"))
```

Define network

```
#sensitivity set
sensitivity <- v
```

```
#vector of studies focusing on populations of primary interest
```

```
pop <- data %>%
  filter(population %in% c("cardiology", "critically ill", "medical", "stroke")) %>%
  pull(study) %>%
  unique()
```

```
#vector of studies with uncommonly used interventions that may add heterogeneity
```

```
int.sparse <- data %>%
  filter(treatment %in% c("vka", "tar", "heparinoid")) %>%
  pull(study) %>%
  unique()
```

```
#vector of studies with unclear specification of vte outcomes
```

```
unclear <- c("Kapoor1999", "Mccarthy1986")
```

```
#main data for analyses
```

```
v <- v %>%
  filter(study %in% pop & !study %in% int.sparse & !study %in% unclear)
```

```
#basic descriptives
```

```
dscr <- data.prep(arm.data = v,
  varname.t = "treatment",
  varname.s = "study")
```

```
char <- net.tab(data = dscr,
  outcome = "responders",
  N = "sampleSize",
  type.outcome = "binomial",
  time = NULL)
```

R code for main and node-splitting models

```
#network summary statistics
char$network
#network summary statistics by treatment
char$intervention
#network summary statistics according to direct comparisons
char$comparison

#network of all eligible trials, numbers represent direct comparisons
network <- mtc.network(data = v, treatments = treat.code[treat.code$id %in% v$treatment,])
net.plot(dscr, node.scale = 2, edge.scale=2,study.counts=TRUE)
```

Define and run the model

```
#define NMA model
model <- mtc.model(network,
  linearModel = "random",
  type = "consistency",
  likelihood = "binom",
  link = "logit",
  n.chain = 4,
  hy.prior = mtc.hy.prior("std.dev", "dunif", 0, "om.scale")) #set vague prior for between study heterogeneity

#run model
v.mcmc <- mtc.run(model,
  n.adapt = 50000, #burn-in
  n.iter = 250000, #iterations
  thin = 10)
```

Algorithm convergence

```
#algorithm convergence, iteration plots
plot(v.mcmc)
gelman.plot(v.mcmc)

#overall PSFR
diag <- gelman.diag(v.mcmc); diag$psrf; diag$mpsrf
```

Model fit

```
v.mcmc$deviance$Dbar #residual deviance
v.mcmc$deviance$data.points #total data points
v.mcmc$deviance$pD #effective parameters
v.mcmc$deviance$DIC #deviance information criterion

deviance <- mtc.deviance(v.mcmc)

#residual deviance plot
mtc.devplot.annotated(deviance)

#leverage plot
mtc.levplot.annotated(deviance)
```

Consistency: nodesplitting

```
#assessment of consistency
v.nodesplit <- mtc.nodesplit(network,
  linearModel = "random",
  n.adapt = 50000,
  n.iter = 250000,
  thin = 10)
```

R code for main and node-splitting models

```
#consistency evaluation leads to numerical instability in the ufh_low vs none comparison most likely due to sparse events
plot(summary(v.nodesplit))

#convergence plots of the VTE nodesplitting without continuity correction
plot(v.nodesplit$d.none.ufh_low)

#transform data to relative effects using the pairwise function from the netmeta package, applying a continuity correction of 0.5 to 0 event studies
v2 <- pairwise(treat = v$treatment,
  event = v$responders,
  n = v$sampleSize,
  studlab = v$study,
  data = v,
  reference.group="placebo",
  incr=0.5,
  sm="OR")

#select appropriate columns and transform the data to the format required by the gemtc package
v2 <- as_tibble(v2)
v2 <- v2 %>%
  select(study, treat1, treat2, TE, seTE) %>%
  pivot_longer(-study,
    names_to = c(".value"),
    names_pattern = "(.*)" %>%
  set_colnames(c("study", "treatment", "diff", "std.err"))

#multi-arm trials
v2 %>%
  pull(study) %>%
  table() %>%
  {.[. > 2]}

#remove redundant rows in multi-arm trials that were created when pivoting data and calculate base arm SE (assuming correlation=0.5)
multi1 <- v2 %>%
  group_by(study) %>%
  filter(study %in% c("Kay1995", "Samama1999", "Levi2007")) %>%
  slice(1:3) %>%
  mutate(std.err = ifelse(is.na(std.err), lag(std.err)*lead(std.err)*0.5, std.err))

multi2 <- v2 %>%
  filter(study == "Ist1997") %>%
  slice(3:5) %>%
  mutate(std.err = ifelse(is.na(std.err), lag(std.err)*lead(std.err)*0.5, std.err))

#combine for total dataset
v2 <- v2 %>%
  filter(!study %in% c("Kay1995", "Samama1999", "Ist1997", "Levi2007")) %>%
  full_join(multi1) %>%
  full_join(multi2)

#re-do nodesplitting using relative effects data
network <- mtc.network(data.re = v2)

v2.nodesplit <- mtc.nodesplit(network,
  linearModel = "random",
  likelihood = "binom",
  link = "logit",
```

R code for main and node-splitting models

```
n.adapt = 50000,  
n.iter = 250000,  
thin = 10)
```

Consistency: nodesplitting results

```
mtc.nodesplit.comparisons(network)
```

```
plot(summary(v2.nodesplit))
```

```
# Inferences
```

```
#overall results
```

```
summary(v.mcmc)
```

```
#efficacy compared to none
```

```
forest(relative.effect(v.mcmc, t1 = "none"), use.description = TRUE)
```

```
#efficacy compared to placebo
```

```
forest(relative.effect(v.mcmc, t1 = "placebo"), use.description = TRUE)
```

```
#rank probability
```

```
rank.prob <- rank.probability(v.mcmc, preferredDirection = -1)
```

```
#rankogram
```

```
plot(rank.prob, beside=TRUE, cex.names=0.75)
```

```
#SUCRA
```

```
cumrank.prob <- apply(t(rank.prob), 2, cumsum)
```

```
sucra <- round(colMeans(cumrank.prob[-nrow(cumrank.prob),]),4)
```

```
print(sucra)
```

Calculate mean ranks

```
#calculate mean ranks
```

```
ranks <- rank.prob
```

```
print(ranks)
```

```
meanranks <- as.table(c(
```

```
#DOAC
```

```
meanrank.doac <- 1*ranks[1,1] + 2*ranks[1,2] + 3*ranks[1,3] + 4*ranks[1,4] + 5*ranks[1,5] + 6*ranks[1,6] + 7*ranks[1,7] + 8*ranks[1,8],
```

```
#lmwh_int
```

```
meanrank.lmwh_int <- 1*ranks[2,1] + 2*ranks[2,2] + 3*ranks[2,3] + 4*ranks[2,4] + 5*ranks[2,5] + 6*ranks[2,6] + 7*ranks[2,7] + 8*ranks[2,8],
```

```
#lmwh_low
```

```
meanrank.lmwh_low <- 1*ranks[3,1] + 2*ranks[3,2] + 3*ranks[3,3] + 4*ranks[3,4] + 5*ranks[3,5] + 6*ranks[3,6] + 7*ranks[3,7] + 8*ranks[3,8],
```

```
#none
```

```
meanrank.none <- 1*ranks[4,1] + 2*ranks[4,2] + 3*ranks[4,3] + 4*ranks[4,4] + 5*ranks[4,5] + 6*ranks[4,6] + 7*ranks[4,7] + 8*ranks[4,8],
```

```
#pentasach
```

```
meanrank.pentasach <- 1*ranks[5,1] + 2*ranks[5,2] + 3*ranks[5,3] + 4*ranks[5,4] + 5*ranks[5,5] + 6*ranks[5,6] + 7*ranks[5,7] + 8*ranks[5,8],
```

```
#placebo
```

```
meanrank.placebo <- 1*ranks[6,1] + 2*ranks[6,2] + 3*ranks[6,3] + 4*ranks[6,4] + 5*ranks[6,5] + 6*ranks[6,6] + 7*ranks[6,7] + 8*ranks[6,8],
```

```
#ufh_int
```

```
meanrank.ufh_int <- 1*ranks[7,1] + 2*ranks[7,2] + 3*ranks[7,3] + 4*ranks[7,4] + 5*ranks[7,5] + 6*ranks[7,6] + 7*ranks[7,7] + 8*ranks[7,8],
```

```
#ufh_low
```

R code for main and node-splitting models

```
meanrank.ufh_low <- 1*ranks[8,1] + 2*ranks[8,2] + 3*ranks[8,3] + 4*ranks[8,4] + 5*ranks[8,5] + 6*ranks[8,6] + 7*ranks[8,7] + 8*ranks[8,8]
))
print(round(meanranks,1))
```

Overview of prior distributions

#between-trial standard deviation:

```
v.mcmc$model$hy.prior
v.mcmc$model$om.scale
```

#trial baselines and effect estimates:

#obtain standard deviation for the relative effects prior (normal distribution).

```
v.mcmc$model$re.prior.sd
```

#calculate the precision:

```
1/(v.mcmc$model$re.prior.sd^2)
```

Calculate prediction intervals

#rename treatments to numeric

```
tmp <- v %>% mutate(treatment = ifelse(treatment=="placebo",1,
  ifelse(treatment=="none",2,
  ifelse(treatment=="lmwh_low",3,
  ifelse(treatment=="lmwh_int",4,
  ifelse(treatment=="ufh_low",5,
  ifelse(treatment=="ufh_int",6,
  ifelse(treatment=="pentasach",7,
  ifelse(treatment=="doac",8,NA))))))))))
```

#redefine the network in order to retrieve the data in the format required for the gemtc rjags code

```
network <- mtc.network(data = tmp)
```

```
model <- mtc.model(network,
  linearModel = "random",
  type = "consistency",
  likelihood = "binom",
  link = "logit",
  n.chain = 4,
  hy.prior = mtc.hy.prior("std.dev", "dunif", 0, "om.scale"))
```

```
dat <- model$dat
```

#define the rjags code, based on gemtc output and supplemented to calculate prediction intervals

```
model <- "model {
  # Likelihood for arm-based data
  for (i in studies.a) {
    for (k in 1:na[i]) {
      logit(p[i, k]) <- mu[i] + delta[i, k]
      r[i, k] ~ dbin(p[i, k], n[i, k])

      rhat[i, k] <- p[i, k] * n[i, k]
      dev[i, k] <- 2 *
        (r[i, k] * (log(r[i, k]) - log(rhat[i, k])) +
        (n[i, k] - r[i, k]) * (log(n[i, k] - r[i, k]) - log(n[i, k] - rhat[i, k])))
    }
  }
  # Likelihood for contrast-based data (univariate for 2-arm trials)
```

R code for main and node-splitting models

```
## OMITTED
# Likelihood for contrast-based data (multivariate for multi-arm trials)
## OMITTED

# Random effects model
for (i in studies) {
  # Study-level relative effects
  w[i, 1] <- 0
  delta[i, 1] <- 0
  for (k in 2:na[i]) { # parameterize multi-arm trials using a trick to avoid dnorm
    delta[i, k] ~ dnorm(md[i, k], tau.d[i, k])
    md[i, k] <- d[t[i, 1], t[i, k]] + sw[i, k]
    tau.d[i, k] <- tau.d * 2 * (k - 1) / k
    w[i, k] <- delta[i, k] - (d[t[i, 1], t[i, k]])
    sw[i, k] <- sum(w[i, 1:(k-1)]) / (k - 1)
  }
}

# Random effects variance prior
sd.d ~ dunif(0, om.scale)
tau.d <- pow(sd.d, -2)

# Relative effect matrix
d[1, 1] <- 0
d[1, 2] <- d.1.5 + d.5.2
d[1, 3] <- d.1.3
d[1, 4] <- d.1.4
d[1, 5] <- d.1.5
d[1, 6] <- d.1.3 + d.3.6
d[1, 7] <- d.1.7
d[1, 8] <- d.1.4 + d.4.8
for (i in 2:nt) {
  for (j in 1:nt) {
    d[i, j] <- d[1, j] - d[1, i]
  }
}

prior.prec <- pow(re.prior.sd, -2)

# Study baseline priors
for (i in studies.a) {
  mu[i] ~ dnorm(0, prior.prec)
}

# Effect parameter priors
d.1.3 ~ dnorm(0, prior.prec)
d.1.4 ~ dnorm(0, prior.prec)
d.1.5 ~ dnorm(0, prior.prec)
d.1.7 ~ dnorm(0, prior.prec)
d.3.6 ~ dnorm(0, prior.prec)
d.4.8 ~ dnorm(0, prior.prec)
d.5.2 ~ dnorm(0, prior.prec)

# Prediction intervals
pred.d.12 ~ dnorm(d[1, 2], tau.d)
pred.d.13 ~ dnorm(d[1, 3], tau.d)
pred.d.14 ~ dnorm(d[1, 4], tau.d)
pred.d.15 ~ dnorm(d[1, 5], tau.d)
```

R code for main and node-splitting models

```
pred.d.16 ~ dnorm(d[1, 6], tau.d)
pred.d.17 ~ dnorm(d[1, 7], tau.d)
pred.d.18 ~ dnorm(d[1, 8], tau.d)

# Prediction intervals (odds ratio scale)
pred.or.12 <- exp(pred.d.12)
pred.or.13 <- exp(pred.d.13)
pred.or.14 <- exp(pred.d.14)
pred.or.15 <- exp(pred.d.15)
pred.or.16 <- exp(pred.d.16)
pred.or.17 <- exp(pred.d.17)
pred.or.18 <- exp(pred.d.18)
}"
#fit and run model
model.fit <- jags.model(file=textConnection(model), data = dat, n.chains = 4)

update(model.fit, 50000)

samples <- coda.samples(model.fit, n.iter=250000, thin = 10, variable.names = c("sd.d", "pred.or.12", "pred.or.13", "pred.or.14", "pred.or.15", "pred.or.16", "pred.or.17", "pred.or.18"))
#convergence
plot(samples, trace=TRUE, density = TRUE)

#prediction interval credible intervals
pred <- as.data.frame(summary(samples)[2]) %>%
  rownames_to_column() %>%
  select(rowname, quantiles.2.5., quantiles.50., quantiles.97.5.) %>%
  rename(comp = rowname, ci.l = quantiles.2.5., median=quantiles.50., ci.u=quantiles.97.5.) %>%
  mutate_if(is.numeric, round,2)

print(pred)
```

Network meta-analysis of major bleeding

```
#load helper functions
source(here("Functions", "functions.R"), local = knitr::knit_global())

#load data files
load(here("Data", "data.RData"))

# Define network
#sensitivity set
sensitivity <- b

#vector of studies focusing on populations of primary interest
pop <- data %>%
  filter(population %in% c("cardiology", "critically ill", "medical", "stroke")) %>%
  pull(study) %>%
  unique()

#vector of studies with uncommonly used interventions that may add heterogeneity
int.sparse <- data %>%
  filter(treatment %in% c("vka", "tar", "heparinoid")) %>%
  pull(study) %>%
  unique()

#main data, excluding uncommonly used interventions
```

R code for main and node-splitting models

```
b <- b %>%
  filter(study %in% pop & !study %in% int.sparse)

#basic descriptives
dscr <- data.prep(arm.data = b,
  varname.t = "treatment",
  varname.s = "study")

char <- net.tab(data = dscr,
  outcome = "responders",
  N = "sampleSize",
  type.outcome = "binomial",
  time = NULL)

#network summary statistics
char$network
#network summary statistics by treatment
char$intervention
#network summary statistics according to direct comparisons
char$comparison

#network of all eligible trials, numbers represent direct comparisons
network <- mtc.network(data = b, treatments = treat.code[treat.code$id %in% b$treatment,])
net.plot(dscr, node.scale = 2, edge.scale=2,study.counts=TRUE)
```

Define and run the model

```
#define NMA model
model <- mtc.model(network,
  linearModel = "random",
  type = "consistency",
  likelihood = "binom",
  link = "logit",
  n.chain = 4,
  hy.prior = mtc.hy.prior("std.dev", "dunif", 0, "om.scale")) #set vague prior for between study heterogeneity

#run model
b.mcmc <- mtc.run(model,
  n.adapt = 50000, #burn-in
  n.iter = 250000, #iterations
  thin = 10)
```

Algorithm convergence

```
#algorithm convergence, iteration plots and prior densities
plot(b.mcmc)
gelman.plot(b.mcmc)

#overall PSFR
diag <- gelman.diag(b.mcmc); diag$psrf; diag$mpsr
```

Model fit

```
b.mcmc$deviance$Dbar #residual deviance
b.mcmc$deviance$data.points` #total data points
b.mcmc$deviance$pD #effective parameters
b.mcmc$deviance$DIC #deviance information criterion

deviance <- mtc.deviance(b.mcmc)
```

R code for main and node-splitting models

```
#residual deviance plot  
mtc.devplot.annotated(deviance)
```

```
#leverage plot  
mtc.levplot.annotated(deviance)
```

Consistency: nodesplitting

```
#assessment of consistency
```

```
b.nodesplit <- mtc.nodesplit(network,  
  linearModel = "random",  
  n.adapt = 50000,  
  n.iter = 250000,  
  thin = 10)
```

```
#consistency evaluation is suggestive of remaining inconsistency.  
plot(summary(b.nodesplit))
```

#Upon closer inspection this inconsistency is probably caused by the UFH low vs LMWH low direct comparison. This comparison is informed by 3 studies that detected only 1 bleeding event in the lmwh_low arm, whereas they detected 8 bleeding events in the UFH_low arms

```
b %>% filter(study %in% c("Aquino1990","Forette1995","Bergmann1996"))
```

#This translates into a very large and imprecise direct intervention effect, that very likely also influences the indirect estimate of uf_h_int vs lmwh_low. Although it's possible (and maybe even likely) that UFH low truly performs worse than lmwh low, we would argue this inconsistency is mainly driven by sparse events and sampling variation. Therefore we do not regard this as problematic.

Inferences

```
#overall results  
summary(b.mcmc)
```

```
#efficacy compared to none  
forest(relative.effect(b.mcmc, t1 = "none"), use.description = TRUE)
```

```
#efficacy compared to placebo  
forest(relative.effect(b.mcmc, t1 = "placebo"), use.description = TRUE)
```

```
#rank probability  
rank.prob <- rank.probability(b.mcmc, preferredDirection = -1)
```

```
#rankogram  
plot(rank.prob, beside=TRUE, cex.names=0.75)
```

```
#SUCRA  
cumrank.prob <- apply(t(rank.prob), 2, cumsum)  
sucra <- round(colMeans(cumrank.prob[-nrow(cumrank.prob),]),4)  
print(sucra)
```

Calculate mean ranks

```
#calculate mean ranks  
ranks <- rank.prob  
print(ranks)
```

```
meanranks <- as.table(c(  
#DOAC
```

```
meanrank.doac <- 1*ranks[1,1] + 2*ranks[1,2] + 3*ranks[1,3] + 4*ranks[1,4] + 5*ranks[1,5] + 6*ranks[1,6] + 7*ranks[1,7] + 8*ranks[1,8],  
#lmwh_int
```

```
meanrank.lmwh_int <- 1*ranks[2,1] + 2*ranks[2,2] + 3*ranks[2,3] + 4*ranks[2,4] + 5*ranks[2,5] + 6*ranks[2,6] + 7*ranks[2,7] + 8*ranks[2,8],
```

R code for main and node-splitting models

```
#lmwh_low
meanrank.lmwh_low <- 1*ranks[3,1] + 2*ranks[3,2] + 3*ranks[3,3] + 4*ranks[3,4] + 5*ranks[3,5] + 6*ranks[3,6] + 7*ranks[3,7] + 8
*ranks[3,8],
#none
meanrank.none <- 1*ranks[4,1] + 2*ranks[4,2] + 3*ranks[4,3] + 4*ranks[4,4] + 5*ranks[4,5] + 6*ranks[4,6] + 7*ranks[4,7] + 8*rank
s[4,8],
#pentasach
meanrank.pentasach <- 1*ranks[5,1] + 2*ranks[5,2] + 3*ranks[5,3] + 4*ranks[5,4] + 5*ranks[5,5] + 6*ranks[5,6] + 7*ranks[5,7] + 8
*ranks[5,8],
#placebo
meanrank.placebo <- 1*ranks[6,1] + 2*ranks[6,2] + 3*ranks[6,3] + 4*ranks[6,4] + 5*ranks[6,5] + 6*ranks[6,6] + 7*ranks[6,7] + 8*r
anks[6,8],
#ufh_int
meanrank.ufh_int <- 1*ranks[7,1] + 2*ranks[7,2] + 3*ranks[7,3] + 4*ranks[7,4] + 5*ranks[7,5] + 6*ranks[7,6] + 7*ranks[7,7] + 8*ra
nks[7,8],
#ufh_low
meanrank.ufh_low <- 1*ranks[8,1] + 2*ranks[8,2] + 3*ranks[8,3] + 4*ranks[8,4] + 5*ranks[8,5] + 6*ranks[8,6] + 7*ranks[8,7] + 8*r
anks[8,8]
))

print(round(meanranks,1))
```

Overview of prior distributions

```
#between-trial standard deviation:
b.mcmc$model$hy.prior
b.mcmc$model$om.scale

#trial baselines and effect estimates:
#obtain standard deviation for the relative effects prior (normal distribution).
b.mcmc$model$re.prior.sd

#calculate the precision:
1/(b.mcmc$model$re.prior.sd^2)
```

Calculate prediction intervals

```
#rename treatments to numeric
tmp <- b %>% mutate(treatment = ifelse(treatment=="placebo",1,
  ifelse(treatment=="none",2,
  ifelse(treatment=="lmwh_low",3,
  ifelse(treatment=="lmwh_int",4,
  ifelse(treatment=="ufh_low",5,
  ifelse(treatment=="ufh_int",6,
  ifelse(treatment=="pentasach",7,
  ifelse(treatment=="doac",8,NA))))))))))

#redefine the network in order to retrieve the data in the format required for the gemtc rjags code
network <- mtc.network(data.ab = tmp)

model <- mtc.model(network,
  linearModel = "random",
  type = "consistency",
  likelihood = "binom",
  link = "logit",
  n.chain = 4,
  hy.prior = mtc.hy.prior("std.dev", "dunif", 0, "om.scale"))

dat <- model$dat
```

R code for main and node-splitting models

```
inits <- model$inits

#define the rjags code, based on gemtc output and supplemented to calculate prediction intervals
model <- "model {
  # Likelihood for arm-based data
  for (i in studies.a) {
    for (k in 1:na[i]) {
      logit(p[i, k]) <- mu[i] + delta[i, k]
      r[i, k] ~ dbin(p[i, k], n[i, k])

      rhat[i, k] <- p[i, k] * n[i, k]
      dev[i, k] <- 2 *
        (r[i, k] * (log(r[i, k]) - log(rhat[i, k])) +
          (n[i, k] - r[i, k]) * (log(n[i, k] - r[i, k]) - log(n[i, k] - rhat[i, k])))
    }
  }
  # Likelihood for contrast-based data (univariate for 2-arm trials)
  ## OMITTED
  # Likelihood for contrast-based data (multivariate for multi-arm trials)
  ## OMITTED

  # Random effects model
  for (i in studies) {
    # Study-level relative effects
    w[i, 1] <- 0
    delta[i, 1] <- 0
    for (k in 2:na[i]) { # parameterize multi-arm trials using a trick to avoid dnorm
      delta[i, k] ~ dnorm(md[i, k], tau.d[i, k])
      md[i, k] <- d[t[i, 1], t[i, k]] + sw[i, k]
      tau.d[i, k] <- tau.d * 2 * (k - 1) / k
      w[i, k] <- delta[i, k] - (d[t[i, 1], t[i, k]])
      sw[i, k] <- sum(w[i, 1:(k-1)]) / (k - 1)
    }
  }

  # Random effects variance prior
  sd.d ~ dunif(0, om.scale)
  tau.d <- pow(sd.d, -2)

  # Relative effect matrix
  d[1, 1] <- 0
  d[1, 2] <- -d.3.1 + d.3.5 + d.5.2
  d[1, 3] <- -d.3.1
  d[1, 4] <- -d.3.1 + d.3.4
  d[1, 5] <- -d.3.1 + d.3.5
  d[1, 6] <- -d.3.1 + d.3.6
  d[1, 7] <- d.1.7
  d[1, 8] <- -d.3.1 + d.3.4 + d.4.8
  for (i in 2:nt) {
    for (j in 1:nt) {
      d[i, j] <- d[1, j] - d[1, i]
    }
  }

  prior.prec <- pow(re.prior.sd, -2)

  # Study baseline priors
  for (i in studies.a) {
```

R code for main and node-splitting models

```
mu[i] ~ dnorm(0, prior.prec)
}

# Effect parameter priors
d.1.4 ~ dnorm(0, prior.prec)
d.1.7 ~ dnorm(0, prior.prec)
d.3.1 ~ dnorm(0, prior.prec)
d.3.4 ~ dnorm(0, prior.prec)
d.3.5 ~ dnorm(0, prior.prec)
d.3.6 ~ dnorm(0, prior.prec)
d.4.8 ~ dnorm(0, prior.prec)
d.5.2 ~ dnorm(0, prior.prec)

# Prediction intervals
pred.d.12 ~ dnorm(d[1, 2], tau.d)
pred.d.13 ~ dnorm(d[1, 3], tau.d)
pred.d.14 ~ dnorm(d[1, 4], tau.d)
pred.d.15 ~ dnorm(d[1, 5], tau.d)
pred.d.16 ~ dnorm(d[1, 6], tau.d)
pred.d.17 ~ dnorm(d[1, 7], tau.d)
pred.d.18 ~ dnorm(d[1, 8], tau.d)

# Prediction intervals (odds ratio scale)
pred.or.12 <- exp(pred.d.12)
pred.or.13 <- exp(pred.d.13)
pred.or.14 <- exp(pred.d.14)
pred.or.15 <- exp(pred.d.15)
pred.or.16 <- exp(pred.d.16)
pred.or.17 <- exp(pred.d.17)
pred.or.18 <- exp(pred.d.18)
}"
#fit and run model
model.fit <- jags.model(file=textConnection(model), data = dat, n.chains = 4)

update(model.fit, 50000)

samples <- coda.samples(model.fit, n.iter=250000, thin = 10, variable.names =
c("sd.d", "pred.or.12", "pred.or.13", "pred.or.14", "pred.or.15", "pred.or.16", "pred.or.17", "pred.or.18"))
#convergence
plot(samples, trace=TRUE, density = TRUE)

#prediction interval credible intervals
pred <- as.data.frame(summary(samples)[2]) %>%
  rownames_to_column() %>%
  select(rowname, quantiles.2.5., quantiles.50., quantiles.97.5.) %>%
  rename(comp = rowname, ci.l = quantiles.2.5., median=quantiles.50., ci.u=quantiles.97.5.) %>%
  mutate_if(is.numeric, round,2)

print(pred)
```

Network meta-analysis of SAE

```
#load helper functions
source(here("Functions", "functions.R"), local = knitr::knit_global())

#load data files
load(here("Data", "data.RData"))
```

R code for main and node-splitting models

Define network

```
#sensitivity set
sensitivity <- s

#vector of studies focusing on populations of primary interest
pop <- data %>%
  filter(population %in% c("cardiology", "critically ill", "medical", "stroke")) %>%
  pull(study) %>%
  unique()

#vector of studies with uncommonly used interventions that may add heterogeneity
int.sparse <- data %>%
  filter(treatment %in% c("vka", "tar", "heparinoid")) %>%
  pull(study) %>%
  unique()

#main data, excluding uncommonly used interventions
s <- s %>%
  filter(study %in% pop & !study %in% int.sparse)

#basic descriptives
dscr <- data.prep(arm.data = s,
  varname.t = "treatment",
  varname.s = "study")

char <- net.tab(data = dscr,
  outcome = "responders",
  N = "sampleSize",
  type.outcome = "binomial",
  time = NULL)

#network summary statistics
char$network
#network summary statistics by treatment
char$intervention
#network summary statistics according to direct comparisons
char$comparison

#network of all eligible trials, numbers represent direct comparisons
network <- mtc.network(data = s, treatments = treat.code[treat.code$id %in% s$treatment,])
net.plot(dscr, node.scale = 2, edge.scale=2,study.counts=TRUE)
```

Define and run the model

```
#define NMA model
model <- mtc.model(network,
  linearModel = "random",
  type = "consistency",
  likelihood = "binom",
  link = "logit",
  n.chain = 4,
  hy.prior = mtc.hy.prior("std.dev", "dunif", 0, "om.scale")) #set vague prior for between study heterogeneity

#run model
s.mcmc <- mtc.run(model,
  n.adapt = 50000, #burn-in
  n.iter = 250000, #iterations
  thin = 10)
```

R code for main and node-splitting models

Algorithm convergence

```
#algorithm convergence, iteration plots and prior densities  
plot(s.mcmc)  
gelman.plot(s.mcmc)
```

#overall PSFR

```
diag <- gelman.diag(s.mcmc); diag$psrf; diag$mpsr
```

Model fit

```
s.mcmc$deviance$Dbar #residual deviance  
s.mcmc$deviance$`data points` #total data points  
s.mcmc$deviance$pD #effective parameters  
s.mcmc$deviance$DIC #deviance information criterion
```

```
deviance <- mtc.deviance(s.mcmc)
```

#residual deviance plot

```
mtc.devplot(deviance)
```

#leverage plot

```
mtc.levplot(deviance)
```

Consistency: nodesplitting

#assessment of consistency

```
s.nodesplit <- mtc.nodesplit(network,  
                             linearModel = "random",  
                             n.adapt = 50000,  
                             n.iter = 250000,  
                             thin = 10)
```

#No evidence of inconsistency but some estimates appear unstable probably due to sparse events.

```
plot(summary(s.nodesplit))
```

Consistency: nodesplitting results

```
mtc.nodesplit.comparisons(network)
```

#the continuity correction does not appear to make a significant difference here

```
plot(summary(s2.nodesplit))
```

Inferences

#overall results

```
summary(s.mcmc)
```

#efficacy compared to placebo

```
forest(relative.effect(s.mcmc, t1 = "placebo"), use.description = TRUE)
```

#rank probability

```
rank.prob <- rank.probability(s.mcmc, preferredDirection = -1)
```

#rankogram

```
plot(rank.prob, beside=TRUE, cex.names=0.75)
```

#SUCRA

```
cumrank.prob <- apply(t(rank.prob), 2, cumsum)  
sucra <- round(colMeans(cumrank.prob[-nrow(cumrank.prob),]),4)  
print(sucra)
```

R code for main and node-splitting models

Calculate mean ranks

```
#calculate mean ranks
ranks <- rank.prob
print(ranks)

meanranks <- as.table(c(
#lmwh_int
meanrank.lmwh_int <- 1*ranks[1,1] + 2*ranks[1,2] + 3*ranks[1,3] + 4*ranks[1,4] + 5*ranks[1,5],
#lmwh_low
meanrank.lmwh_low <- 1*ranks[2,1] + 2*ranks[2,2] + 3*ranks[2,3] + 4*ranks[2,4] + 5*ranks[2,5],
#placebo
meanrank.placebo <- 1*ranks[3,1] + 2*ranks[3,2] + 3*ranks[3,3] + 4*ranks[3,4] + 5*ranks[3,5],
#ufh_int
meanrank.ufh_int <- 1*ranks[4,1] + 2*ranks[4,2] + 3*ranks[4,3] + 4*ranks[4,4] + 5*ranks[4,5],
#ufh_low
meanrank.ufh_low <- 1*ranks[5,1] + 2*ranks[5,2] + 3*ranks[5,3] + 4*ranks[5,4] + 5*ranks[5,5]
))

print(round(meanranks,1))
```

Overview of prior distributions

```
#between-trial standard deviation:
s.mcmc$model$hy.prior
s.mcmc$model$om.scale

#trial baselines and effect estimates:
#obtain standard deviation for the relative effects prior (normal distribution).
s.mcmc$model$re.prior.sd

#calculate the precision:
1/(s.mcmc$model$re.prior.sd^2)
```

Calculate prediction intervals

```
#rename treatments to numeric
tmp <- s %>% mutate(treatment = ifelse(treatment=="placebo",1,
  ifelse(treatment=="lmwh_low",2,
  ifelse(treatment=="lmwh_int",3,
  ifelse(treatment=="ufh_low",4,
  ifelse(treatment=="ufh_int",5,NA))))))

#redefine the network in order to retrieve the data in the format required for the gemtc rjags code
network <- mtc.network(data = tmp)

model <- mtc.model(network,
  linearModel = "random",
  type = "consistency",
  likelihood = "binom",
  link = "logit",
  n.chain = 4,
  hy.prior = mtc.hy.prior("std.dev", "dunif", 0, "om.scale"))

dat <- model$dat

#define the rjags code, based on gemtc output and supplemented to calculate prediction intervals
model <- "model {
  # Likelihood for arm-based data
  for (i in studies.a) {
```

R code for main and node-splitting models

```
for (k in 1:na[i]) {
  logit(p[i, k]) <- mu[i] + delta[i, k]
  r[i, k] ~ dbin(p[i, k], n[i, k])

  rhat[i, k] <- p[i, k] * n[i, k]
  dev[i, k] <- 2 *
    (r[i, k] * (log(r[i, k]) - log(rhat[i, k])) +
     (n[i, k]-r[i, k]) * (log(n[i, k] - r[i, k]) - log(n[i, k] - rhat[i, k])))
}
}
# Likelihood for contrast-based data (univariate for 2-arm trials)
## OMITTED
# Likelihood for contrast-based data (multivariate for multi-arm trials)
## OMITTED

# Random effects model
for (i in studies) {
  # Study-level relative effects
  w[i, 1] <- 0
  delta[i, 1] <- 0
  for (k in 2:na[i]) { # parameterize multi-arm trials using a trick to avoid dnorm
    delta[i, k] ~ dnorm(md[i, k], tau.d[i, k])
    md[i, k] <- d[t[i, 1], t[i, k]] + sw[i, k]
    tau.d[i, k] <- tau.d * 2 * (k - 1) / k
    w[i, k] <- delta[i, k] - (d[t[i, 1], t[i, k]])
    sw[i, k] <- sum(w[i, 1:(k-1)]) / (k - 1)
  }
}

# Random effects variance prior
sd.d ~ dunif(0, om.scale)
tau.d <- pow(sd.d, -2)

# Relative effect matrix
d[1, 1] <- 0
d[1, 2] <- d.1.2
d[1, 3] <- d.1.3
d[1, 4] <- d.1.2 + d.2.4
d[1, 5] <- d.1.2 + d.2.5
for (i in 2:nt) {
  for (j in 1:nt) {
    d[i, j] <- d[1, j] - d[1, i]
  }
}

prior.prec <- pow(re.prior.sd, -2)

# Study baseline priors
for (i in studies.a) {
  mu[i] ~ dnorm(0, prior.prec)
}

# Effect parameter priors
d.1.2 ~ dnorm(0, prior.prec)
d.1.3 ~ dnorm(0, prior.prec)
d.2.4 ~ dnorm(0, prior.prec)
d.2.5 ~ dnorm(0, prior.prec)
```

R code for main and node-splitting models

```
# Prediction intervals
pred.d.12 ~ dnorm(d[1, 2], tau.d)
pred.d.13 ~ dnorm(d[1, 3], tau.d)
pred.d.14 ~ dnorm(d[1, 4], tau.d)
pred.d.15 ~ dnorm(d[1, 5], tau.d)

# Prediction intervals (odds ratio scale)
pred.or.12 <- exp(pred.d.12)
pred.or.13 <- exp(pred.d.13)
pred.or.14 <- exp(pred.d.14)
pred.or.15 <- exp(pred.d.15)
}"
#fit and run model
model.fit <- jags.model(file=textConnection(model), data = dat, n.chains = 4)

update(model.fit, 50000)

samples <- coda.samples(model.fit, n.iter=250000, thin = 10, variable.names = c("sd.d", "pred.or.12", "pred.or.13", "pred.or.14", "pred.or.15"))
#convergence
plot(samples, trace=TRUE, density = TRUE)

#prediction interval credible intervals
pred <- as.data.frame(summary(samples)[2]) %>%
  rownames_to_column() %>%
  select(rowname, quantiles.2.5., quantiles.50., quantiles.97.5.) %>%
  rename(comp = rowname, ci.l = quantiles.2.5., median=quantiles.50., ci.u=quantiles.97.5.) %>%
  mutate_if(is.numeric, round, 2)

print(pred)
```

R code for main and node-splitting models